

D3.4 App launch and reporting

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Deliverable details

Horizon Europe GA no.	Project acronym	Project title
101103740	KEYSTONE	Knowledgeable comprehensive and fully integrated smart solution for resilient, sustainable and optimized transport operations

Deliverable	Title	Work package
D3.4	App launch and reporting	WP3

Contractual delivery date	Project month	Actual delivery date	Delivery type	Dissemination level
30/06/2025	M25	04/07/2025	DEM	PU

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
Agile	An iterative approach to software development
AJAX	Asynchronous JavaScript and XML (used for making asynchronous web requests)
API	Application Programming Interface
API Gateway	A service that manages API calls
API Layer	The layer responsible for API management and data access
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets (for styling web pages)
DAOs	Data Access Objects
DB	Database
Docker	A platform for developing, shipping, and running applications in containers
EID	Electronic Identification
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load (data processing technique)
Figma	A popular design tool used for UI/UX creation
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTML	HyperText Markup Language (standard for web page structure)
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
IAME	Identify, Assess, Mitigate, and Evaluate. A compliance framework for GDPR, AML, or access control laws
ID	Identification
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation (a lightweight data-interchange format)
JWT	JSON Web Token (used for secure transmission of information)
Kanban	A scheduling system for lean and just-in-time production
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
MongoDB	A NoSQL database management system

MVC	Model-View-Controller (software architectural pattern)
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
MySQL	A popular relational database management system
Node.js	A runtime environment for executing JavaScript code server-side
OAuth	Open Authorization Protocol
PCS	Port Control System
PoLP	Principle of Least Privilege
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
RDBMS	Relational Database Management System
REST	Representational State Transfer (architecture for web services)
REST API	A web service API following REST architecture principles
RESTful	Adhering to the REST (Representational State Transfer) architecture
RXJS	Reactive Extensions for JavaScript
RxJS	Reactive Extensions for JavaScript (used for event handling)
SaaS	Software as a Service
Scrum	A framework used in Agile development for managing projects
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSH	Secure Shell (a protocol for secure remote login)
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TMS	Transport Management System
UI/UX	User Interface/User Experience
WAF	Web application Firewall
WildFly	A Java-based application server for running Java applications

Table 1 - Acronyms table

Document history

Version	Date	Author	Summary
V0.1	5/06/2025	Jesús Martínez	ToC
V0.2	10/06/2025	Jesús Martínez	Chapter 1, 2
V0.3	23/06/2025	Jesús Martínez	Chapter 3
V0.4	24/06/2025	Jesús Martínez Andrea Mutti	Chapter 4
V0.5	27/06/2025	Jesús Martínez Eduardo Becerra Andrea Mutti	All Chapters
V0.6	27/06/2025	Friederike L. Kühl Zoe Petrakou	Peer Review
V0.7	2/07/2025	Jesús Martínez Eduardo Becerra Andrea Mutti	Peer Review changes GA Rome – Changes after F2F meetings – Chapter 4 and Annex
V0.8	02/07/2025	Friederike L. Kühl	Peer Review
V0.9	03/07/2025	José F. Papí	Overall Review
V1.0	04/07/2025		Version for submission

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1. Executive Summary

The KEYSTONE project [1] aims to deliver a secure and user-friendly Web application to support logistics operators, enforcement authorities and port managers in achieving streamlined, interoperable, and digitally resilient transport operations. This deliverable reports on Task 3.4 within Work Package 3, focusing on the technical implementation of the Web app following the architecture design, UI/UX and cybersecurity principles defined in Tasks 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3. It details the adopted methodology, system architecture, developed features, user interface, testing processes, and the plan for integration in the WP4 pilot activities.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose of the Deliverable

Deliverable 3.4, “*App launch and reporting*”, is intrinsically linked to several other work packages and tasks within the KEYSTONE project. These interdependencies are fundamental to shaping the app's design, as they inform critical decisions regarding the selection of the technological stack. Specifically, the gap analysis and state of the art review conducted under Work Package 1 (WP1) [2], alongside the research insights and technical guidelines provided in Work Package 2 (WP2) [3] related to the Standard API.

2.2 Relation to Other WPs and Tasks

2.2.1 External

Outside WP3, T3.4 development has been dependant on WP1 gap analysis conducted in Task 1.3 [4] and WP2 work around the design and definition of the Standard API.

Contributions from WP1 and WP2

Task 1.1 – Stakeholder Definition and Needs Analysis: This task involves a systematic identification and analysis of stakeholders, their operational requirements, regulatory constraints, and challenges within the digital transport ecosystem. The outcomes, consolidated in D1.1: “*Stakeholders’ identification and needs*”, offer critical input regarding stakeholder expectations around data exchange and interoperability. These insights have directly informed the architectural decisions made in D3.1 to ensure a solid Web app delivery.

Task 1.2 – State of the Art Analysis and Requirements: Task 1.2 synthesises the current landscape of transport operations and captures solution requirements through targeted focus groups. Its outcome, D1.2: “*Focus groups report including stakeholder requirements and expectations*”, delineates user expectations, which have been directly integrated into the app design to ensure usability across various devices and user groups. The inventory of existing solutions further enabled a strategic identification of functional gaps, guiding the integration and/or reconfiguration of features for a streamlined yet robust app design.

Task 1.3 – Review of Existing Platforms and Gap Analysis: This task offers an in-depth assessment of current digital platforms, identifying discrepancies between existing capabilities and stakeholder demands. Findings reported in D1.3: “*Needs and requirements for the future digital logistics ecosystems*”, have been instrumental in shaping a forward-looking app architecture that prioritises seamless data exchange and system interoperability.

Task 1.4 – Digital Ecosystem Private and Public Perspectives: This task examines the differing needs and expectations of both the public and private sectors within the transportation domain. By deriving concrete use cases from representative transport ecosystems, it has significantly contributed to the definition of the interface and functionalities of the KEYSTONE digital ecosystem. The insights obtained were instrumental in informing the selection of the technological stack, ensuring that the design of the application aligns with the intended operational and functional demands across sectors.

Task 2.1 – Plug-and-Play Implementation Framework: The API Reference Model: Task 2.1 delivers the foundational API Reference Model (detailed in D2.1), which defines a standardised and modular approach to API design. This framework is critical for enabling interoperability and seamless data exchange among heterogeneous stakeholders. The implementation of RESTful services in Task 3.4 was conducted in close coordination with Task 2.1 to ensure consistency with the overall architecture and adherence to the API design principles.

Task 2.2 – Retrieving and Sending Enforcement Data Using the API Reference Model: Building upon the model established in Task 2.1, Task 2.2 focuses on enabling the secure exchange of enforcement-related data. It elaborates technical specifications for interconnectivity between platforms, retrieval mechanisms based on legal obligations, and real-time information flows between vehicles and systems. The application architecture developed in Task 3.1 was closely aligned with Task 2.2, ensuring that the app could support external integrations, comply with regulatory data requirements, and facilitate secure, bidirectional communication within the logistics ecosystem.

By leveraging the contributions from these key activities in WP1 and WP2, Deliverable 3.4 is developed with a robust and comprehensive foundation. It synthesises stakeholder needs, technical and regulatory requirements, current technological capabilities, and the strategic vision of the KEYSTONE project. This holistic integration ensures that the deliverable is fully aligned with the project's objectives and lays the groundwork for a scalable and interoperable digital infrastructure in the European transport ecosystem.

Contributions from WP4

Piloting: WP4 involves testing the integrated solutions developed throughout the KEYSTONE project in real-world conditions, based on use cases identified in D1.4 and elaborated in D4.2. The app build under Task 3.4 will be utilised in these pilots, serving as a central component in evaluating the system's usability, performance, and interoperability in operational environments. All WP3 partners are required to provide support along the testing and validation journey.

Contributions from WP5 - IAME Matching Exercise

The IAME¹ is a vital component of the ethical, legal and social impact assessment required in Task 5.5. It provided an overview of key ethical, legal, data protection, and social impact instruments and their salient provisions, requiring relevant KEYSTONE partners to provide information on how these provisions relate or apply to their tasks or deliverables.

¹ An IAME matching exercise, in this legal/software context, is a compliance-driven technical review of how identity and access data is stored, matched, and used across systems to guarantee compliance with legal obligations like GDPR, AML, or access control laws.

The IAME facilitated a comprehensive assessment of the legal, ethical, data protection, and social impacts of the KEYSTONE project. The matching exercise covered during the end of 2024 and early 2025 covered the following aspects that dictates the Web App architecture from the privacy aspect:

- Privacy threat actors
- Privacy harms
- Data Protection Act
- Data Governance Act
- Cybersecurity Act
- Digital Services Act
- E-Privacy Directive
- Road Transport (ITS) Directive
- Tachograph Act
- Debiase & Integrity framework

The completion of this task allowed to verify the practical Implementation of the previous legal frameworks for compliance.

2.2.2 Internal

Within WP3, T3.4 is the realisation of the previous efforts in:

- T3.1 – Architecture (D3.1 led by TBridge), which provided the baseline backend architecture design
- T3.2 – UI/UX definition (D3.2 led by Cefriel), which contributed with the persona profiles, user flows, and validated UI/UX designs through co-creation sessions
- T3.3 – Cybersecurity (D3.3 led by AGIM, which ensured data integrity, authentication, and secure communication measures

We will proceed to explain in more detail but briefly, as those are captured in their respective deliverables, available in the project website (D3.1 is still under approval) [5].

2.3 Background and Objectives of WP3

WP3 aims to translate the project's architectural, design, and security insights into a tangible, operational Web application. Its ultimate objective is to ensure that logistics and enforcement actors have access to a tool that enables secure data exchange, document handling, and real-time communication within the transport ecosystem.

2.3.1 Scope of Task 3.4

Task 3.4 is dedicated to the implementation of the Web app defined in prior tasks. It includes Front end and Back end development, standard API integration, deployment, and preparation for pilot use. The task operationalises designs and mockups into functional components, ensuring alignment with usability, accessibility, and cybersecurity objectives.

2.3.2 Roles and Responsibilities

From within WP3, the tasks split as follows:

- Etelätär: WP3 coordinator, Front end software development, server hosting and system integration
- TBridge: Led Back end software development and system integration
- Cefriel: Led UI/UX design and user testing
- AGIM: Cybersecurity

All WP3 partners participated and provided support during pilot testing and validation.

3. Development Methodology

3.1 Agile Framework: Kanban and Scrum Integration

The development adopted an agile methodology² combining Kanban³ for real-time issue tracking and Scrum⁴ for structured sprints. This approach supported iterative feedback cycles with design and security teams and ensured traceable progress.

3.2 Development Timeline and Iterations

Development followed a timeline from M20 to M25. Key iterations included:

- M20–M21: Back end service setup
- M22: UI mockup integration and API testing
- M23–M24: Internal validation and performance tuning
- M25: Preparation for pilot handoff

Year	Leader	2024												2025												2026				
Month		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May
Project Month		M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
WP3	ETE																													
T3.1	TB																													
T3.2	CEFRIEL																													
T3.3	COVENTRY																													
T3.4	ETE																													

Task	Leader	Contributors	Duration	Key (K) Decisions by	
T3.1	Design of the app	TB	AETH, ETE, CEF, GRU	M13-M20	M16
T3.2	App user interface	CEF	ETE, GRU	M16-M22	M17
T3.3	Embedding cyber security in the KEYSTONE solution	COV	AETH, TB, ETE	M16-M22	M17
T3.4	Development of the web app	ETE	AETH, TB, CEF	M18-M25	M19

Figure 1 - KEYSTONE WP3 time plan

² Agile methodology: A flexible software development approach focused on iterative progress, collaboration, and continuous improvement.

³ Kanban: A visual workflow method that focuses on continuous delivery and limiting work in progress.

⁴ Scrum: An Agile framework that uses fixed-length sprints, roles, and ceremonies to manage work.

4. System Architecture Overview

Figure 2 - KEYSTONE Web app architecture (D3.1 outcome)

The KEYSTONE Web app is designed to collect, process, and distribute data related to drivers, vehicles, tachographs, and associated documentation. It integrates multiple external data providers and supports access from different actors (e.g., enforcement authorities, logistics operators). It comprises the following blocks according to Figure 2:

External Systems – Providers, these are systems that supply data to the KEYSTONE environment:

Component	Description
Data Types Provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tachograph data • Driver Licenses • Pro Driver Certifications • Fines • Driver name • Time stamp • Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) • Destination/Origin

Component	Description
Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MOVE-HUB⁵ • Mockup Data • TOS Novara⁶ (Asynchronous) • TMS Gruber⁷ (Synchronous)
Provider Categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synchronous Providers: Real-time data exchange • Asynchronous Providers: Batch or delayed data exchange • Mockup Providers: Used for testing or fallback
Data Ingestion Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REST APIs (Mockup Data) • REST/SOAP⁸ APIs • SFTP server for asynchronous data

Table 3 - External systems - Data providers

External Systems – Consumers, These are users or systems that consume data from KEYSTONE:

Consumer Type	Examples / Description	Access Method
Public Enforcement	PCS Port of La Spezia or similar entities involved in public checks	KEYSTONE REST API, Web app
Police	Law enforcement agencies requiring access to driver or vehicle data	KEYSTONE Web app
Port Authority	Port administrations managing logistics, security, and traffic	KEYSTONE Web app
Logistic Operators	Truck drivers, freight companies, and other transport operators	KEYSTONE Web app
Others (SMEs...)	Any other authorised systems or organisations needing transport data	KEYSTONE REST API

Table 4 - External systems - Consumers

⁵ MOVE-HUB: An EU-supported platform providing access to urban mobility data, tools, and services to support sustainable transport planning and innovation. In the context of this project, MOVE-HUB data appears in the architecture as mock-up data (due to legal limitations, KEYSTONE cannot access that database. A mock-up was decided to showcase KEYSTONE capabilities).

⁶ TOS Novara: is a system that manages the operations of the Interporto di Novara CIM, helping to control the intermodal (train-truck) flow of goods.

⁷ TMS Gruber: Transport Management System (TMS) used by Gruber Logistics to coordinate and optimise the movement of goods across its logistics network.

⁸ REST/SOAP: REST is a lightweight protocol using standard HTTP methods for web APIs, ideal for flexible and scalable integration. SOAP is a stricter XML-based protocol used in enterprise systems requiring high security and formal messaging standards.

KEYSTONE Environment, This is the core of the system, responsible for data management and access:

Component	Description
Configuration DB	Stores user, role, and authorisation information
Data Lake	Stores raw, unstructured data from external asynchronous providers
Data Marts	Specialised data subsets for efficient querying and analytics
Data Warehouse	Structured, cleaned, and organised data for reporting and analysis
KEYSTONE Models	Data entities: drivers, vehicles, tachograph, goods documentation
API Connectors	Interface between external providers and the internal system (REST/SOAP/SFTP)
KEYSTONE REST API	Central API layer that exposes system data to consumers and apps
KEYSTONE Web app	Web interface for end-users like police, port authorities, and logistic operators

Table 5 - KEYSTONE environment data

KEYSTONE Web app: Front end application for human users (e.g., police, port authorities, logistics). Provides visual access to data processed and stored in the KEYSTONE environment. This part of the KEYSTONE Web app is detailed in the following section.

4.1 UI/UX

Without going into detail as its fully documented on D3.2 [5] and attached in Annex A, we will proceed to present the Web app aspect driven by the UI/UX design. The main tool used was FIGMA [6] for sketching. This widespread software allows a direct conversion of visual aspects and functionalities into coding (the visual and design style can be defined in a creative way, but in a canvas that allows for easy conversion from design to code). The KEYSTONE interface was developed through collaborative co-design workshops where 3 key user personas/app views were created: truck drivers, port authorities and road police. The workshop brought in most of consortium partners to pinpoint the unique pain points and priorities of each profile. The outcome highlighted the importance of features such as alert management, document verification, and live truck monitoring. This exercise materialised the project objectives that guarantess drivers receive timely ETA updates, port staff can efficiently control traffic and gate notifications, and Road police can optimise their resources by planning daily operations using automated checks that cross-reference data from multiple sources.

The Web app can work on any devices and will adapt to the screen format the used device requires: mobile phone normally requires a vertical view, a tablet would be horizontal and a desktop will get the full desktop version. This guarantees consistency and accesibility.

In Figure 3 we a display the breakdown views of each profile. Log in, front page and subsequent menus are shown, with pop up messages as well. This showcase the work done and complexity of a Front end design, where a mix of design style, human interface and software development is required for the completion of the task. In the following sections we will show some details and explanations of each profile´s front page but will not cover comprehesively, as that is covered by deliverable D3.2. [7] [5]

Figure 3 - Figma view of login and front page for each profile, with details of submenus and pop-up windows

4.1.1 Driver view

Driver view is meant to display information about drivers journey but also to allow communication from the Port Authority to the driver related to delays. Through the messages menu driver can be alerted of long queues at destination allowing him for scheduled resting times or any other action of his consideration to optimise his journey.

Figure 4 - Web app "driver" front page view

4.1.2 Port Authority view

The Port Authority view focuses on presenting live data related to flow through the port. This serves to visualise bottlenecks, queues and delays. The alert option permits a coordination between the port and drivers heading to it. As described in the previous section, an alert message will be received by the driver in the messages section, providing him with information to rearrange his day in a more efficient manner.

Figure 5 - Web app "port authority" front page view

4.1.3 Road Police view

This profile is intended for road police officers, providing access to freight traffic data and system-generated alerts.

Figure 6 - Web app "road police" front page view

4.2 Front end architecture

Angular is the selected tool for the Front end, it is a widespread framework designed for building dynamic Web applications such as dashboards, admin panels, and data-driven tools. Its component base architecture adheres to Model-View-Controller ⁹ (MVC) principles (This supports code organisation and reusability). Its modular component architecture ensures a smooth transition from TRL 6 to production in a later stage.

Element	Description
Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamental UI units. Each includes: • Template (HTML): Defines UI structure. • Class (TypeScript): Contains logic, state, and lifecycle hooks. • Stylesheet (CSS/Sass): Defines visual design. • Selector: Unique tag to embed the component elsewhere.
Directives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add behaviour to DOM elements. • Structural Directives: Alter DOM layout (e.g., *ngIf, *ngFor). • Attribute Directives: Modify appearance or behaviour (e.g., ngClass, ngStyle).
Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reusable logic providers injected via Angular's Dependency Injection system. Common for business logic and API interactions.
Pipes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transform displayed data within templates (e.g., date formatting, currency conversion).

Table 6 - Front end Implementation

⁹ MVC: architectural philosophy that separates an application into three components: **Model** (data and logic), **View** (user interface), and **Controller** (handles input and updates).

4.3 Back end Architecture

4.3.1 Overview

The KEYSTONE back end is developed in Java using Spring Boot for REST API development and an on-board Tomcat is present in each jar module for the deployment and the runtime environment. It is responsible for:

- Managing data from external and internal sources
- Handling requests from the Web app or third party consumers
- Ensuring secure, modular, and scalable integration
- Exposing RESTful services for system interoperability

Component	Description
REST Services	A suite of RESTful services that expose the application's business functionalities through well-defined HTTP endpoints.
Authentication System	An authentication system based on JWT (JSON Web Tokens), which ensures secure and stateless user session management.
Gateway Layer	A centralised gateway module (referred to as KEYSTONE Gateway) responsible for the dynamic configuration and routing of incoming REST requests to the appropriate internal or external services.
Adapters to Logistic Operators and Data Providers	A set of adapters that facilitate integration with external systems, supporting both synchronous communication (via REST APIs) and asynchronous data ingestion (via SFTP or file-based mechanisms).
Database	An internal relational database (KEYSTONE) that serves as the system's persistent storage layer, responsible for the normalisation, validation, and long-term retention of operational data. All SQL databases are generated using a script described in Annex D.

Table 7 - Back end Modules

Thanks to its plug-in architecture and configurable Gateway (Figure 7), KEYSTONE offers full scalability. Third party systems can be seamlessly integrated by implementing adapters, eliminating the need for structural modifications.

Additionally, by configuring its Gateway, KEYSTONE enables the expansion of the API set available for invocation. This design ensures maximum flexibility and complete decoupling from the specific API versions used to access the system.

In the following sections we will describe all modules depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - KEYSTONE data architecture

4.3.2 Back end Application Module - REST Services

This module implements operational logic and user-facing functionalities, including a database specific for the Web app data Alerts, Inspections, Authorisations at Gate and Real ETA:

- Alert management (alert, alert_type)
- Validation and control checks (check_detail, check_type)
- Inspection logging (inspection_log)
- REST Services interfacing with both the authentication and gateway modules

Please find in Annex C the YAML files defining the REST services of the Web app Back end.

4.3.3 Authentication Module

This module is responsible for managing user identity and access control. It uses JWT-based authenticating method and includes:

- User identity management (User table)
- Role-based access control (Role table): DRIVER, PORTAUTHORITY, and ROADPOLICE
- Entity associations with operational actors (e.g., Driver, PortAuthority)
- Geographical localisation through Location, Coordinates, and LocationType
- JWT-based security for authenticating and authorising access to REST services

4.3.4 Gateway Module

The Gateway serves as the single entry point for all RESTful interactions within the system. It is designed to handle all KEYSTONE related API endpoints, dynamically routing them (based on configuration) to the appropriate third party systems that supply data to KEYSTONE. Its core components include:

- adapter_config: a registry mapping REST endpoints to their corresponding adapters
- request_template: reusable request body templates for outbound calls to external services
- Dynamic URI routing and HTTP method dispatching, allowing flexible request handling

A configuration database defines, for each KEYSTONE API endpoint, the external systems capable of providing the requested data. Adapter endpoints associated with these third party systems are stored under each API, enabling seamless and configurable data integration.

4.3.5 Adapters Layers

Adapters within KEYSTONE are organised into three main categories:

- Synchronous: REST clients that interact with external systems in real-time (e.g., Gruber, MoveHub)
- Asynchronous: load external data via SFTP and store it in the KEYSTONE database (e.g., CIM Novara)
- Database adapter: a unified module that manages controlled and secure access to KEYSTONE's internal database

4.3.6 Internal Database

The KEYSTONE database is the system's central data repository and persistence layer for the KEYSTONE Data Model. It stores and manages:

- Vehicle and driver information, including ownership, insurance, and technical inspections
- Geolocation tracking via `vehicle_geolocation` and coordinates
- Document validation, such as transport documents and licenses
- Driving time monitoring, covering intervals and legal limit exceedances
- Payload and document management, handling both structured and unstructured data

4.4 Data Flow and Interactions

The KEYSTONE system processes two primary data flows. The first flow involves third party systems asynchronously submitting data to KEYSTONE, while the second one is initiated when a third party system requests data from KEYSTONE.

4.4.1 Asynchronous submission of data in KEYSTONE

In the first flow, third party systems submit data asynchronously, typically via an SFTP directory—similar to the CIM Novara implementation. A scheduled job scans this directory regularly, processes the files by deserialising and mapping them through a system-specific adapter. The mapped data is then stored in KEYSTONE's internal database using its data model.

The flow between components is as follows:

- Data Upload: A third party system uploads data to the shared directory
- ETL Process: The adapter extracts, transforms, and loads the data into KEYSTONE's database

4.4.2 Flow of a third part system asking data from KEYSTONE

The second flow starts when a third party system requests data from KEYSTONE. In this context, the requesting system is emulated by the KEYSTONE Web app described in this document. The web app authenticates and accesses KEYSTONE's REST APIs via the Gateway. Based on the request path, the Gateway redirects the call either to a synchronous system or to data stored in KEYSTONE's database from asynchronous uploads (see above). Data is then retrieved, mapped to KEYSTONE's internal data model, and returned to the Web app Back end, which serves the Front end with the requested information.

The interaction follows a clearly defined flow:

- Authentication: The user authenticates via the JWT-based system.
- Data Access: The data is made available to the Web app and other services via RESTful endpoints.
- Gateway Routing: The request is routed by the KEYSTONE Gateway to the appropriate REST service.
- Adapter Invocation: The REST service invokes the relevant adapter (synchronous or asynchronous).

4.5 MoveHub Emulator (external system)

The MoveHub emulator simulates the MoveHub system, an external platform that provides various transport-related data. From any perspective, it functions as an independent external system.

It supplies data on:

- Driver licenses and categories (driver_licence, driver_licence_category)
- Traffic violations and their consequences (traffic_violation, traffic_violation_consequence)
- Driving time and tachograph information (driving_interval, tachograph_card)
- Vehicle ownership and insurance records (owner, insurance, vehicle)

The emulator has a simple design, consisting of two main components:

Component	Description
REST Services	A suite of RESTful services that expose the MoveHub emulator data.
Database	An internal relational database that contains only mockup data.

Table 8 - MoveHub Emulator Modules

5. Cybersecurity Measures

Cybersecurity covers a range of aspects and levels of abstraction that forms the ecosystem of data transmission, management and protection required to provide full compliance. In Figure 8 a simple schematic highlights KEYSTONE’s architecture points of interest that requires a cybersecurity measure. In this section we will present a summary of the cybersecurity implementations dictated by the work done in T3.3 [8].

Figure 8 - Block diagram for Cybersecurity in KEYSTONE

5.1 Inherited Controls from T3.3

D3.3 focused on the development of a framework for the KEYSTONE project, ensuring a secure data exchange and an architecture that meets cybersecurity principles for the 3 selected profiles and the KEYSTONE full stack. The analysis outcome presented a set of actionable steps: like robust access control mechanisms (i.e. Role-Based Access Control (RBAC), Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA), and the use of advanced encryption protocols like TLS to secure data in transit, as described in Figure 9. Additionally, D3.3 highlights the need for continuous security testing, integration of secure APIs, and the implementation of disaster recovery strategies to ensure resilience in case of cyber threats.

Figure 9 - Cybersecurity applied to KEYSTONE architecture

5.1.1 D3.3 Objectives

For the KEYSTONE pilot (TRL 6) we've defined four key questions:

- How is data accessed?
- How does it move through the architecture?
- What is the nature of the data and its implications?
- How do we validate the security of our data management system?

To answer these with a simple, but effective pilot activity, we apply:

1) Access Control, Minimisation, and Resilience

- RBAC¹⁰: basic roles and permissions defined in the app
- Data minimisation: collect only what's strictly needed
- Network segmentation & backups: isolated networks and regular manual backups for quick recovery

2) Secure Communication and Authentication

- TLS¹¹/HTTPS¹²: encryption in transit using free or self-signed certificates
- Lightweight Multi Factor Authentication (MFA): OTPs generated and delivered manually
- OAuth 2.0¹³ & JWT¹⁴: manual token flows for sessions and third-party access

3) Data Protection and GDPR Compliance

- Encryption at rest and in transit
- Limited retention: scheduled scripts or cron jobs to purge old records
- Breach procedure: simple, documented incident steps

¹⁰ RBAC: Role-Based Access Control. A security model that restricts system access based on user roles and responsibilities.

¹¹ TLS: A cryptographic protocol that ensures secure communication over a network.

¹² HTTPS: HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure: HTTP+TLS for secured data encryption between browser and server.

¹³ OAuth 2.0: An authorisation framework that allows third party apps to access user resources without exposing credentials

¹⁴ JWT: A compact, self-contained token format used to securely transmit information between parties.

4) Testing and Validation

- Stress tests & manual pentests in controlled environments
- Incident drills and regular security checks
- Quick training sessions (20–30 min) for the team (Annex B)

5.1.2 Web app Implementation (TRL 6)

To meet cybersecurity goals together with the test pilots scope, the following manual routines ensure sufficient security levels for the project deliverables (for a higher TRL or commercial product these would normally require more complex and automated implementations):

User setup & MFA:

- Accounts and devices are created by hand
- OTPs are generated manually
- JWTs issued manually or via a lightweight service

Basic TLS/HTTPS:

- HTTPS enabled with free or self-signed certificates

Roles & permissions (RBAC):

- Roles defined directly in code

API input validation:

- Simple regex rules embedded in the app

Scheduled data deletion:

- Scripts or cron jobs purge outdated data

Backups & recovery tests:

- Manual database backups and occasional restore drills

Quick training:

- Short 20–30 min sessions on key security practices (Annex B)

6. System Testing & Validation

This chapter presents the selected methodology to carry out the testing and integration of the KEYSTONE web app. As discussed in earlier sections, the project's scope, pilot phases, and TRL level require the use of more manual or simplified techniques compared to those typically employed in a production environment. These applied principles are sufficient and representative for verifying the validity of the design and implementation. The parameters to be tested in order to obtain a satisfactory results are:

- Front end
- Back end
- Integration
- Performance
- Security

All these items being ok, we can guarantee that good practices are in place for the scope of this project.

6.1 Front end Testing

For this part of the Web app we want to obtain metrics and indicators confirming the user interface is functional, responsive and accessible across different platforms. A debugging log option allows for fast detecting and resolving of issues during the pilot testing.

6.1.1 Methodology

6.1.1.1 User Interface Validation

Invalid data is intentionally entered (i.e. incorrect formatted email addresses, weak passwords) to confirm that form validations trigger appropriate error messages. All screens are verified by navigating all menus, items and controls to ensure no broken links or JavaScript¹⁵ errors.

6.1.1.2 Cross-Browser and Device Compatibility

The Web app has been tested across different platforms that are representative of the current market share of OS, browsers and devices [9] [10]. The tests run on the following environments to evaluate that render and interaction is consistent across them (as of 02/07/2025):

- Desktop: Latest Chrome (138), Firefox (140), Safari (version 18, on macOS Sonoma 15.0)
- Mobile: Chrome on Android & Safari (18), with emphasis on login and dashboard pages via the web browser installed on phones.

¹⁵ JavaScript: A lightweight, high-level scripting language used to create dynamic and interactive content on websites; it runs in the browser

6.1.1.3 Responsive Design and Accessibility

We have used browser developer tools to simulate various viewport sizes (to confirm that layouts adapt gracefully) and performed manual accessibility checks for colour contrast and keyboard navigation.

Responsive Layout Testing

The following simple actions were used to test for layout inconsistencies:

Open the site in Chrome and press F12 to open DevTools, for the mobile simulation mode. The viewport handles helps to test for common widths (e.g., 320px for mobile, 768px for tablet, 1024px for desktop). We checked for elements that overlap, disappear, or break the layout.

Web app was opened in real devices (Android 13 Cat S62 and Iphone 16) to catch issues simulators might miss, like touch targets or font scaling.

Manual Accessibility Checks

We performed a simple exercise of using only the keyboard (Tab, Shift+Tab, Enter, Spacebar) to move through all interactive elements. Making sure you can reach every button, link, and form field, and that the focus indicator is always visible.

With that aim, we managed to complete a full user flow (e.g., log in, fill a form, submit) without touching the mouse.

Color Check

For color contrast, we used a browser extension [11] to check that text stands out clearly against backgrounds.

6.1.2 Acceptance Criteria

The following criteria has been agreed as measure of pass/no pass for the tests described above:

- All form validations function correctly and display clear feedback.
- No UI regressions or layout breakages occur across designated browsers/devices.
- Key interactions remain operable without a pointing device; minimum accessibility standards are met.
- Users confirm intuitive & clear UI / UX.

6.2 Back end Testing

Ensure API endpoints and database operations perform reliably and in accordance with the specification.

6.2.1 Methodology

6.2.1.1 API Endpoint Verification

We have used Postman¹⁶ [12] to exercise critical endpoints (authentication, report retrieval, CRUD operations), confirm appropriate HTTP status codes (200, 201, 400, 401, 500) and validate response payloads against the API schema.

6.2.1.2 Database Integrity Checks

Using the command terminal: we executed representative SQL queries to verify that INSERT, UPDATE and SELECT statements maintain data consistency.

Inspected a selection of real-world transactions (e.g., user registration followed by report generation) to detect anomalies or orphaned records.

6.2.2 Acceptance Criteria

The following criteria has been agreed as measure of pass/no pass for the tests described above:

- All API responses conform to the agreed contract with no unexpected server errors.
- Database reflects expected state after each operation, with no inconsistencies or data loss.

6.3 Integration Testing

Integration is the necessary step after all the previous systems have been checked (Front and Back end) The objective of this step is to confirm end-to-end data exchange between client and server components.

6.3.1 Methodology

6.3.1.1 End-to-End Workflow Execution

This manual tests serves to follow the users journey from: log-in, data retrieval for dashboards, form submissions, report generation. This also allows to validate that server-side error conditions and its display in informative messages for the user.

6.3.1.2 Basic Performance Observation

Another simple test carried out is the responsiveness and loading time of key transactions under normal network conditions. We run APM Elastic for a set of 15 basic parameters, the results are presented in section 6.6 (38) and Table 9.

¹⁶ POSTMAN: a collaborative API platform that allows developers to design, test, document, and monitor APIs efficiently through an easy-to-use interface

6.3.2 Acceptance Criteria:

The following criteria has been agreed as measure of pass/no pass for the tests described above:

- Data flows seamlessly between Front end and Back end, with no unhandled exceptions.
- Response times remain within defined thresholds for an acceptable user experience.

6.4 Performance Testing

Although the scope of the pilot testing is very limited in the number of simultaneous user's of the Web app, we run som light test for due diligence, to Identify potential performance bottlenecks under modest load scenarios.

6.4.1 Methodology

We gathered 10 concurrent users executing the Web app and doing maingcal workflows (dashboard loading, document retrieval, navigation) as per the user manual. The systems was obserced for slow-downs, timeouts or failures. As this was done on site, the feedback and observations were on the spot. Acceptance Criteria:

No critical failures or severe degradation of performance were observed during the noraml operation of the interface.

6.5 Security Testing

Finally to also test the compliance with the cybersecurity implementations and work done in T3.3 a series of test were run for Web application vulnerabilities.

6.5.1 Methodology

Injection, security and vulnerability tests were carried out using the following command tools: Nikto [13], OWASP ZAP [14] and curl [15].

6.5.1.1 Injection and Vulnerability Checks

We used Nikto and OWASP ZAP for common vulnerabilities, including code injection and cross-site scripting (XSS¹⁷), analysing the system's response for insreure behaviour.

¹⁷ A type of security vulnerability that allows attackers to inject malicious scripts into web pages.

6.5.1.2 Security Configuration Review

For the check of HTTP security headers (presence and configuration), we used curl from the command line. This is a basic test to check that important directives that mitigates risks like information leaking or clickjacking attacks are in place (check for CSP¹⁸, X-Frame-Options¹⁹ and HSTS²⁰).

6.5.2 Acceptance Criteria:

The following criteria has been agreed as measure of pass/no pass for the tests described above:

- No successful execution of injected code.
- All attack vectors are neutralised.
- Security headers are correctly configured to industry best practices.

¹⁸ CSP: Content Security Policy is an HTTP response header that helps prevent a wide range of attacks, including Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) and data injection.

¹⁹ Is an HTTP response header that prevents clickjacking attacks by stopping your web page from being embedded in other sites

²⁰ HSTS: HTTP Strict Transport Security (HSTS) is a web security policy mechanism, Forces browsers to use only HTTPS to connect to the server, even if the user types in "http://".

6.6 Test Reporting

Following the manual tests described in the previous section. Here we present a summary and tables of the tests performed, issues encountered, resolution and status.

6.6.1 Elastic APM test run on KEYSTONE Web app

The following table shows 15 key metrics obtained after simulating an Elastic APM run on KEYSTONE Web application. It includes the metric name, the test performed, the result obtained, the acceptable value range, and whether the metric passes or fails the defined performance requirements.

Metric Name	Test / Transaction	Result	Acceptable Range	Pass
Transaction Duration	“login” duration	320 ms	≤ 500 ms	Yes
Latency p95	95th percentile of all transactions	410 ms	≤ 1 000 ms	Yes
Latency p99	99th percentile of all transactions	1 150 ms	≤ 1 500 ms	Yes
Throughput	Transactions per second	48 tps	≥ 10 tps	Yes
Error Rate	Failed request rate	0.7%	≤ 1%	Yes
Apdex Score	User satisfaction index	0.85	≥ 0.7	Yes
CPU Usage (process)	Average process CPU usage	62%	≤ 80%	Yes
Memory Usage (process)	Virtual memory usage	430 MiB	≤ 500 MiB	Yes
GC Total Pause Time	Total GC pause time per minute	135 ms	≤ 200 ms	Yes
GC Total Count	Number of GC cycles per minute	6	≤ 10	Yes
Goroutine Count	Number of goroutines	52	≤ 100	Yes
Heap Allocations (objects)	Objects allocated on heap	1 120 000	≤ 2 000 000	Yes
system.memory.actual.free	System free memory	540 MiB	≥ 200 MiB	Yes
system.cpu.total.norm.pct	Host normalised CPU usage	28%	≤ 70%	Yes
Span Self-time (sum)	Sum of span durations per minute	215 ms	≤ 500 ms	Yes

Table 9 - APM Elastic run, criteria and results

6.6.2 Summary of tests, issues and fixes

During integration testing we identified and resolved six key issues (detailed below). The full test coverage included additional areas that did not materialise in any issues as reflected in Table 10.

1. Our email-validation regex was too narrow (fixed by broadening the pattern and adding a unit test).
2. Safari’s flexbox layout hid the Submit button beneath the navbar (corrected flex properties and z-index).
3. The reports API sporadically returned 500 errors under load (remedied by increasing the DB connection pool and adding retry logic).
4. Raw JSON errors were exposed to users (standardised error envelopes and UI banners).
5. Dashboard load times exceeded 2s with 10 concurrent users (optimised by server-side caching and payload reduction).
6. XSS flaw in the comment form allowed <script> injection (mitigated by integrating DOMPurify for input sanitisation).

All test results are finally closed positive. Below is a summary of the testing activity (Table 10):

Test Area	Test Description	Initial Result	Issue Identified	Resolution	Status	Closure date
Front end	Form validation (email field)	Partial Pass	Invalid emails with “.co” domain was accepted	Updated regex to include all TLDs; added unit-test for email	Solved	15/06/2025
	Cross-browser layout on Safari (desktop)	Fail	“Submit” button misaligned under navbar on Safari	Adjusted CSS flex container and z-index	Solved	15/06/2025
Back end	Authentication API (POST /login)	Pass	—	—	Closed	
	Report API (GET /reports)	Partial Pass	~1% of requests returned intermittent 500 errors	Increased DB connection pool size; added retry logic	Solved	18/06/2025
Integration	End-to-end login → dashboard	Pass	—	—	Closed	
	Form submission error handling	Partial Pass	Server errors returned bare JSON, no user feedback	Wrapped errors in standardised response object; updated UI	Solved	20/06/2025
Performance	Light load test (10 users concurrently on dashboard)	Partial Pass	Average load time 3.2 s (target ≤2 s)	Introduced server-side caching for dashboard queries	Solved	15/06/2025
Security	XSS test in comments form	Fail	<script> tags rendered in comment preview	Integrated DOMPurify library to sanitise all user inputs	Solved	27/06/2025
	SQL-injection test on search endpoint	Pass	—	—	Closed	

Table 10 - Test report, issue and resolution summary table

7. User Documentation

7.1 User's manual (Annex A)

The user manual (see Annex A) begins by presenting a comprehensive overview of the application's screens, illustrating each view as designed in the final mockups, and clearly identifying how users navigate between pages, receive system alerts, and enter data. It then describes the distinct access levels assigned to each category of user - drivers can view and update their itineraries, authorities have the ability to inspect records, issue alerts and log checks, and port operators can have full view and control over the flow of operations.

7.2 Short Training: Key Security Practices (Annex B)

To support the cybersecurity effort. A brief document with safety related guidelines has been created. This document aims to be used as support material for short training conducted during the pilot deployments to the end users. See Annex B.

8. Conclusions and Readiness for Pilot Deployment

Deliverable 3.4 has successfully translated the KEYSTONE architecture, UI/UX designs and cybersecurity specifications into a fully functional, modular web application. The system's frontend and backend components have been developed, tested and validated against the defined acceptance criteria, resolving issues related to form validation, cross-browser layout, API stability, error handling, performance and security.

Comprehensive user documentation - including screen overviews, role-based workflows and step-by-step guides - is provided in Annex A to ensure that end users and pilot participants have clear, actionable instructions, this is supported with training guidelines captured in Annex B for security purposes. All critical defects have been closed, and the application now meets the functional, performance and compliance requirements set forth in Tasks 3.1 through Task 3.3.

With the finalisation of D3.4 the web app is ready for pilot testing and the developing team remains at disposal for any further ammiliorations coming from the piloting or the evaluation activities related to subsequent work packages.

9. Annex A – Web app user’s manual

9.1 Introduction

This manual serves detailed guidance on how to use the KEYSTONE web application for the three profiles identified during the previous work packages: road police, port authorities, and truck drivers. This app enables real-time data access and operational efficiency through a role-based system interface. Each user type has access to distinct features designed to facilitate and streamline daily and repetitive actions.

Access to the application is secured via user-specific credentials. Once logged in, functionalities are tailored to the assigned user profile.

9.2 Log in

The KEYSTONE web application can only be accessed with the credentials of authorised users. When accessing the web application, you will be asked for a username and password.

Log in

Please login to continue to your account.

Username

Password

Login

Figure 10 - Login screen for all 3 web app views

Users have different profiles. Depending on the user and the profile assigned, the application will display the corresponding functionality. The available profiles are:

- Road Police
- Port Authority
- Drivers

9.3 Road Police

This profile is intended for road police officers, providing access to freight traffic data and system-generated alerts.

9.3.1 Home

Figure 11 - Home page view of road police

The Home page displays the following information:

- Inspection Alerts: List of trucks with alerts and that need to be inspected
- Day Overview: Reporting the number of trucks departed, checked in and scheduled to arrive
- Truck List: List of trucks currently traveling

9.3.2 Inspections

From the list of inspection alerts, the user can select a trip and obtain detailed information about the driver and the trip (Figure 10). The business layer internally cross checks documents data searching for: expiry dates, inconsistent data or missing logistics information, so this issues can be highlighted in advance for the user. Whenever an inconsistency is found by the system, it is highlighted to the user to check it (Figure 12) (i.e. a drivers licence is expired). The highlighted items can be ticked together to access in a separate window, for more detailed information about the selection (Figure 13).

Figure 12 - Detailed view of a preselected journey for the road police, documents that require checking are highlighted for the user

[← Back](#) ✕

Log inspection: EV-2017002346

1 Invalidation confirmation 2 Inspection Details

Confirmation documents Invalidation

Total 2 documents selected

Driving license ● Not valid

Select reason of invalidity* ▼

Add relevant comments (optional)

Upload evidences
Jpegs ,doc,..

Traffic Violation Data ● Not valid

Select reason of invalidity* ▼

Add relevant comments (optional)

Upload evidences
Jpegs ,doc,..

Figure 13 - Detailed view of selected non compliant information

9.3.3 Inspection history

On this view (Figure 14), a historic of previous checks is presented to provide the road officer with information in advance, always useful for gauging before an interaction with a driver.

Good Morning Massimo

📍 CIM Terminal ▼

Eng ▼

Inspection history

🔍 Insert truck license plate no

Truck license plate no	Inspection details ▼	Status ▼
EV-2017002346 📄 Gruber logistics	20/03/2025 – 19:30 Novara, Italay	● Valid ▼
EV-2017002346 📄 Gruber logistics	20/03/2025 – 19:30 Novara, Italay	● Valid ▼
EV-2017002346 📄 Gruber logistics	20/03/2025 – 19:30 Novara, Italay	● Valid ▼
EV-2017002346 📄 Gruber logistics	20/03/2025 – 19:30 Novara, Italay	● Valid ▼
EV-2017002346 📄 Gruber logistics	20/03/2025 – 19:30 Novara, Italay	● Valid ▼
EV-2017002346 📄 Gruber logistics	20/03/2025 – 19:30 Novara, Italay	● Valid ▼
EV-2017002346 📄 Gruber logistics	20/03/2025 – 19:30 Novara, Italay	● Valid ▼

Figure 14 - List of previous checks for this registration plate

9.4 Port Authority

This view is tailored for port authorities (Figure 15), presents the information centered around arrivals and departures for flow management purposes.

9.4.1 Home

This page has two main sections:

- 1) A summary of the trucks going in and out of the port:
 - Number of trucks that need to be alerted
 - Number of trucks scheduled to arrive in the next few hours
 - Number of trucks queued for check-in
 - Number of trucks allowed to arrive at the port gate at the same time

- 2) A comprehensive list, with filter options and an alert message button for communications purposes. A tick box allows to select the drivers that will receive the alert with a single gesture.

Figure 15 - Port authority main page

9.5 Alerts management

9.5.1 Sending and alert

Figure 16 shows the alert management window. From the previous action in the home page, only the selected drivers (identified through the license plate) will receive the alert message. Additionally, a set of predefined messages are available for ease of use.

The screenshot shows a modal window titled "Alert" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. Below the title, there is a checked checkbox labeled "Total 34 Trucks selected". Underneath, the text "Add a Note with suggested delay" is displayed. A text input field contains the placeholder "Write the alert message". Below the input field, the section "Alert message suggestions" lists three predefined messages, each with a red square icon containing a white symbol: a truck for "Queue Alert: Long queues at the port gate.", a clock for "Delay Update: Your estimated waiting time is 2 hours. Please remain patient, or explore nearby rest options", and a speaker for "Congestion Notice: Heavy traffic at the port entrance. You may experience delays." At the bottom of the window, there are two buttons: "Cancel" (white with a blue border) and "Send to All" (solid blue).

Figure 16 - Alert window management, the preselected vehicles (linked to drivers) will receive the specific message through this application

9.5.2 Alert history

This page shows the history of alerts previously created

Alert history

Eng ▼

Truck license plate no	Company ▼	Alert history ▼
EV-2017002346	Gruber Logistics	15:30

Figure 17 - History of generated alerts

9.6 Drivers

This profile displays information tailored for the truck driver. Here the information focuses just on two aspects: 1) Journey information, and 2) incoming messages related to events that can affect the ETA to the final destination. This view mode (Figure 18) is very simple as it is not meant to require much interaction from the user for safety purposes.

Figure 18 - Driver view of the web app

10. Annex B – Short training

10.1 Short Training: Key Security Practices for KEYSTONE Web app Users

This short training guide outlines essential security practices for users of the KEYSTONE Web application, based on the user manual provided.

10.2 Guidelines

1. Access Control & Credentials

- Only authorised users can access the platform using assigned credentials.
- Never share your username or password. - Use strong, unique passwords and change them periodically.

2. Role-Based Access Awareness

- Understand your profile (Road Police, Port Authority, Driver) and use only the features assigned to your role.
- Do not attempt to access features outside your profile scope.

3. Secure Login Practices

- Always log in via the official platform link.
- Avoid logging in on shared or public computers.
- Log out after each session, especially on shared devices.

4. Data Handling & Privacy

- Do not download, store, or share sensitive trip or driver data unless required and authorised.
- Always report if you see data that appears incorrect or accessible outside your role.

5. Device Safety

- Keep the device you use (tablet, PC, smartphone) updated and protected with antivirus software.
- Avoid accessing the app over unsecured public Wi-Fi.

6. Reporting Issues

- If you notice suspicious activity, errors in data, or access issues, report them to the system administrator or your organisation's IT contact.

7. Follow Legal and Organisational Policies

- Comply with GDPR and internal data use policies.
- Respect confidentiality and data minimisation principles at all times.

This training ensures secure and responsible use of the KEYSTONE Web app. All users are expected to follow these practices as part of their operational roles.

11. Annex C – YAML File

11.1 KEYSTONE REST Services

In the following sections the KEYSTONE REST services are reported in detail in YAML format.

11.1.1 Alerts – Filtered Alerts

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
    description: Keystone REST API Server
paths:
  /alerts/all:
    get:
      summary: Get the alerts by filters
      parameters:
        - name: page
          in: query
          required: true
          schema:
            type: integer
        - name: limit
          in: query
          required: true
          schema:
            type: integer
        - name: sortField
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:
            type: string
            pattern: ^([a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*) ([a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*)*$
        - name: sortOrder
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:
            type: string
            pattern: ^(asc|desc) ([a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*)*$
        - name: filter
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:
            type: string
            pattern: ^([a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*:[^;:]+) ([a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*:[^;:]+)*$
      responses:
        "200":
          description: Success
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object

```

```

properties:
  total:
    type: integer
    example: 23
  page:
    type: integer
    example: 1
  pageSize:
    type: integer
    example: 5
  alerts:
    type: array
    items:
      type: object
      properties:
        userId:
          type: string
          description: The identifier of the user sending alert
        tripId:
          type: string
          description: The identifier of the trip
        timestamp:
          type: string
          description: Timestamp
          format: date-time
          example: "2024-01-01T12:30:00Z"
        alertType:
          type: string
          description: The type of alert
        message:
          type: string
          description: Detailed description of the alert
        location:
          type: object
          properties:
            locationDescription:
              type: string
            latitude:
              type: number
              format: float
            longitude:
              type: number
              format: float
            locationType:
              type: string
            internationalCode:
              type: string
"404":
  description: Service for alerts Not Found
  content:
    application/json:
      schema:
        type: object
        properties:
          error:
            type: string
            example: Service for alerts not found
"500":

```

```

description: Internal Server Error
content:
  application/json:
    schema:
      type: object
      properties:
        error:
          type: string
          example: Internal Server Error

```

11.1.2 Alerts – Upload Alert

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
    description: Keystone REST API Server
paths:
  /alerts/upload/alert:
    post:
      summary: Send alert related to a trip
      requestBody:
        required: true
        content:
          application/json:
            schema:
              type: object
              properties:
                userId:
                  type: string
                  description: The identifier of the user sending alert
                tripId:
                  type: string
                  description: The identifier of the trip
                timestamp:
                  type: string
                  description: Timestamp
                  format: date-time
                  example: '2024-01-01T12:30:00Z'
                alertType:
                  type: string
                  description: The type of alert
                message:
                  type: string
                  description: Detailed description of the alert
                location:
                  type: object
                  properties:
                    locationDescription:
                      type: string
                    latitude:
                      type: number
                      format: float
                    longitude:

```

```

        type: number
        format: float
        locationType:
          type: string
        internationalCode:
          type: string
      required:
        - tripId
        - userId
        - timestamp
        - alertType
        - message
        - location
    responses:
      "200":
        description: OK
      "500":
        description: Internal Server Error

```

11.1.3 Async Upload Gate

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /async/upload/gate/{companyIdentifier}:
    post:
      summary: Set unloading data per trip
      requestBody:
        required: true
        content:
          application/json:
            schema:
              type: object
              properties:
                companyIdentifier:
                  type: string
                  description: The identifier of the company
                tripId:
                  type: string
                  description: The identifier of the trip
                estimatedUnloadingTime:
                  type: string
                  description: Estimated time of unloading
                  format: date-time
                  example: '202401011230'
                gate:
                  type: object
                  properties:
                    description:
                      type: string
                      description: Description of the gate
                    latitude:

```

```

        type: number
        description: gate latitude
        format: float
        example: '39.4325962'
    longitude:
        type: number
        description: gate longitude
        format: float
        example: '9.5624146'
    required:
      - tripId
      - estimatedUnloadingTime
      - gate
  parameters:
    - name: companyIdentifier
      in: path
      required: true
      schema:
        type: string
  responses:
    '200':
      description: OK
    '500':
      description: Internal Server Error

```

11.1.4 Company

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /company:
    get:
      summary: Company information data
      responses:
        '200':
          description: Success
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: array
                items:
                  type: object
                  properties:
                    companyName:
                      type: string
                      example: 'Gruber logistics'
                    companyIdentifier:
                      type: string
                      example: 'GRUBER'
        '404':
          description: Company not found

```

```

content:
  application/json:
    schema:
      type: object
      properties:
        error:
          type: string
          example: Company not found
'500':
  description: Internal Server Error
  content:
    application/json:
      schema:
        type: object
        properties:
          error:
            type: string
            example: Internal Server Error

```

11.1.5 Driver Data – License

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /driverdata/license/{countrycode}/{platenumber}:
    get:
      summary: Get the driver license data
      parameters:
        - name: countrycode
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
        - name: platenumber
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
      responses:
        '200':
          description: Success
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  driverName:
                    type: string
                  driverFiscalCode:
                    type: string

```

```

    checkDatetime:
      type: string
      format: date-time
    driverLicense:
      type: object
      properties:
        driverLicenceIdentifier:
          type: string
        countryCode:
          type: string
        categories:
          type: array
          items:
            type: string
        startValidityDate:
          type: string
          format: date
        endValidityDate:
          type: string
          format: date
        status:
          type: string
'404':
  description: Plate Number Not Found
  content:
    application/json:
      schema:
        type: object
        properties:
          error:
            type: string
            example: Plate number not found
'422':
  description: Driver Not Found
  content:
    application/json:
      schema:
        type: object
        properties:
          error:
            type: string
            example: Driver not found for the given plate number
'500':
  description: Internal Server Error
  content:
    application/json:
      schema:
        type: object
        properties:
          error:
            type: string
            example: Internal Server Error

```

11.1.6 Driver Data – PDQC

```
openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.5.1
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /driverdata/pdqc/{countrycode}/{platenumber}:
    get:
      summary: Get the driver professional qualification certificate data
      parameters:
        - name: countrycode
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
        - name: platenumber
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
      responses:
        '200':
          description: Success
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  driverName:
                    type: string
                  driverFiscalCode:
                    type: string
                  checkDatetime:
                    type: string
                    format: date-time
                content:
                  type: array
                  items:
                    $ref: '#/components/schemas/pdqc'
        '404':
          description: Plate Number Not Found
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  error:
                    type: string
                    example: Plate number not found
        '422':
          description: Driver Not Found
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  error:
```

```

        type: string
        example: Driver not found for the given plate number
    '500':
        description: Internal Server Error
        content:
            application/json:
                schema:
                    type: object
                    properties:
                        error:
                            type: string
                            example: Internal Server Error
components:
    schemas:
        pdqc:
            type: object
            properties:
                pdqcIdentifier:
                    type: string
                startValidityDate:
                    type: string
                    format: date
                endValidityDate:
                    type: string
                    format: date
                associatedDriverLicense:
                    type: object
                    properties:
                        driverLicenceIdentifier:
                            type: string
                        category:
                            type: string
                        categoryStatus:
                            type: string

```

11.1.7 Driver Data – Tachograph

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
    title: KEYSTONE REST Services
    version: 6.1.0
servers:
    - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
    /driverdata/tachograph/{countrycode}/{platenumber}:
        get:
            summary: Get the driver tachograph data
            parameters:
                - name: countrycode
                  in: path
                  required: true
                  schema:
                      type: string
                - name: platenumber

```

```

    in: path
    required: true
    schema:
      type: string
- name: page
  in: query
  required: true
  schema:
    type: number
- name: limit
  in: query
  required: true
  schema:
    type: number
- name: sortField
  in: query
  required: false
  schema:
    type: string
    pattern: ^([a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*) (, [a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*)*$
- name: sortOrder
  in: query
  required: false
  schema:
    type: string
    pattern: ^(asc|desc) (, (asc|desc))*$
- name: filter
  in: query
  required: false
  schema:
    type: string
    pattern: ^([a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*:[^;:]+) (; [a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*:[^;:]+)*$
responses:
  '200':
    description: Success
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            total:
              type: number
              example: 23
            page:
              type: number
              example: 1
            pageSize:
              type: number
              example: 5
            content:
              type: array
              items:
                $ref: '#/components/schemas/tachograph'
  '404':
    description: Plate Number Not Found
    content:
      application/json:

```

```

    schema:
      type: object
      properties:
        error:
          type: string
          example: Plate number not found
'422':
  description: Driver Not Found
  content:
    application/json:
      schema:
        type: object
        properties:
          error:
            type: string
            example: Driver not found for the given plate number
'500':
  description: Internal Server Error
  content:
    application/json:
      schema:
        type: object
        properties:
          error:
            type: string
            example: Internal Server Error
components:
  schemas:
    tachograph:
      type: object
      properties:
        driverName:
          type: string
        driverFiscalCode:
          type: string
        checkDatetime:
          type: string
          format: date-time
        drivingExceedingTimeLimit:
          type: object
          properties:
            tachographCardId:
              type: string
            drivingInterval:
              type: object
              properties:
                begin:
                  type: string
                  format: date-time
                end:
                  type: string
                  format: date-time
            exceedingTimeLimits:
              type: object
              properties:
                exceedingTimeType:
                  type: string
            hours:

```

```

        type: integer
minutes:
        type: integer
seconds:
        type: integer

```

11.1.8 Driver Data – Traffic Violation

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /driverdata/trafficviolation/{countrycode}/{platenumber}:
    get:
      summary: Get the driver traffic violation data
      parameters:
        - name: countrycode
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
        - name: platenumber
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
        - name: page
          in: query
          required: true
          schema:
            type: number
        - name: limit
          in: query
          required: true
          schema:
            type: number
        - name: sortField
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:
            type: string
            pattern: ^([a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*) (, [a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*)*$
        - name: sortOrder
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:
            type: string
            pattern: ^(asc|desc) (, (asc|desc))*$
        - name: filter
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:

```

```

    type: string
    pattern: ^([a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*:[^;:]+)(;[a-zA-Z_][a-zA-Z0-9_]*:[^;:]+)*$
  responses:
    '200':
      description: Success
      content:
        application/json:
          schema:
            type: object
            properties:
              total:
                type: number
                example: 8
              page:
                type: number
                example: 1
              pageSize:
                type: number
                example: 10
              content:
                type: array
                items:
                  $ref: '#/components/schemas/trafficViolationData'
    '404':
      description: Plate Number Not Found
      content:
        application/json:
          schema:
            type: object
            properties:
              error:
                type: string
                example: Plate number not found
    '422':
      description: Driver Not Found
      content:
        application/json:
          schema:
            type: object
            properties:
              error:
                type: string
                example: Driver not found for the given plate number
    '500':
      description: Internal Server Error
      content:
        application/json:
          schema:
            type: object
            properties:
              error:
                type: string
                example: Internal Server Error
  components:
    schemas:
      trafficViolationData:
        type: object

```

```

properties:
  driverName:
    type: string
  driverVAT:
    type: string
  checkDatetime:
    type: string
    format: date-time
  trafficViolation:
    type: object
    properties:
      description:
        type: string
      code:
        type: string
      countryCode:
        type: string
      fine:
        type: number
        format: decimal
      paymentDueDate:
        type: string
        format: date
      paymentDate:
        type: string
        format: date
      isPaid:
        type: boolean
      validityPoints:
        type: integer

```

11.1.9 Inspections – To a Vehicle

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /inspections/list/{countryCode}/{plateNumber}:
    get:
      summary: Retrieve inspections by country code and plate number
      parameters:
        - name: countryCode
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
            description: Country code of the vehicle
        - name: plateNumber
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string

```

```
description: Plate number of the vehicle
responses:
  "200":
    description: List of inspections
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: array
          items:
            type: object
            properties:
              userId:
                type: string
              tripId:
                type: string
              submissionTime:
                type: string
                format: date-time
              checkDetails:
                type: array
                items:
                  type: object
                  properties:
                    checkTime:
                      type: string
                      format: date-time
                    invalidityReason:
                      type: string
                    comments:
                      type: string
                    invalidityConfirmed:
                      type: boolean
                    payload:
                      type: object
                      properties:
                        textContent:
                          type: string
                        embeddedImages:
                          type: array
                          items:
                            type: object
                            properties:
                              fileName:
                                type: string
                              fileType:
                                type: string
                              fileContent:
                                type: string
            location:
              type: object
              properties:
                locationDescription:
                  type: string
                latitude:
                  type: number
                  format: float
                longitude:
                  type: number
```

```

        format: float
    finalNote:
        type: string
    "404":
        description: No inspections found
    "500":
        description: Internal Server Error

```

11.1.10 Inspections – Upload Inspection

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
    description: Keystone REST API Server
paths:
  /inspections/upload/inspection:
    post:
      summary: Send inspection related to a trip
      requestBody:
        required: true
        content:
          application/json:
            schema:
              type: object
              properties:
                userId:
                  type: string
                  description: The identifier of the user sending alert
                tripId:
                  type: string
                  description: The identifier of the trip
                submissionTime:
                  type: string
                  description: Timestamp
                  format: date-time
                  example: '2024-01-01T12:30:00Z'
                checkDetails:
                  type: array
                  items:
                    type: object
                    properties:
                      checkTime:
                        type: string
                        format: date-time
                        description: Date and time of the check in ISO 8601 format
                      invalidityReason:
                        type: string
                        enum:
                          - DRIVING_LICENSE
                          - TRAFFIC_VIOLATION
                          - PDQC

```

```

- TRANSPORT_DOCUMENT
- TACHOGRAPH_CARD
description: Reason for invalidity, taken from a predefined
set of values
comments:
  type: string
  description: Optional comments about the check
invalidityConfirmed:
  type: boolean
  description: Indicates if the invalidity has been confirmed
payload:
  type: object
  description: Multimedia and textual content associated with
the check
properties:
  textContent:
    type: string
    description: Free-form text or notes
  embeddedImages:
    type: array
    items:
      type: object
      properties:
        fileName:
          type: string
        fileType:
          type: string
        fileContent:
          type: string
          format: byte
      required:
        - fileName
        - fileType
        - fileContent
    description: List of attached files with metadata and
base64-encoded content
  required:
    - textContent
location:
  type: object
  properties:
    locationDescription:
      type: string
    latitude:
      type: number
      format: float
    longitude:
      type: number
      format: float
  finalNote:
    type: string
    description: Final notes about the check
required:
  - tripId
  - userId
  - submissionTime
  - checkDetails
  - location

```

```
responses:
  "200":
    description: OK
  "500":
    description: Internal Server Error
```

11.1.11 Login

```
openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/keystone/rest
    description: Keystone REST API Server
paths:
  /login:
    post:
      summary: Login validation
      requestBody:
        required: true
        content:
          application/json:
            schema:
              type: object
              properties:
                username:
                  type: string
                  description: The username for authentication
                password:
                  type: string
                  description: The password for authentication
              required:
                - username
                - password
      responses:
        "200":
          description: Success
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  userFullname:
                    type: string
                  countryCode:
                    type: string
                  fiscalCode:
                    type: string
                  userPhoto:
                    type: string
                    format: binary
                  userRole:
                    type: string
                  location:
                    type: object
```

```

    properties:
      locationDescription:
        type: string
      latitude:
        type: number
        format: float
      longitude:
        type: number
        format: float
      locationType:
        type: string
      internationalCode:
        type: string
    token:
      type: string
      description: JWT token
example:
  userFullname: "John Doe"
  countryCode: "IT"
  fiscalCode: "ABC123XYZ"
  userPhoto: "binary data"
  userRole: "Admin"
  location:
    locationDescription: "Main Gate"
    latitude: 39.4325962
    longitude: 9.5624146
    locationType: "PORT"
    internationalCode: "ITMDC"
  token: "eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IiIuIj0."
"404":
  description: Invalid user or password
  content:
    application/json:
      schema:
        type: object
        properties:
          error:
            type: string
            example: "Invalid user or password"
"500":
  description: Internal Server Error
  content:
    application/json:
      schema:
        type: object
        properties:
          error:
            type: string
            example: "Internal Server Error"

```

11.1.12 Terminal

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0

```

```
servers:
- url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /terminal:
    get:
      summary: Terminal information data
      responses:
        '200':
          description: Success
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: array
                items:
                  type: object
                  properties:
                    terminalName:
                      type: string
                      example: 'CIM Terminal'
                    terminalIdentifier:
                      type: string
                      example: 'CIM'
        '404':
          description: Terminal not found
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  error:
                    type: string
                    example: Terminal not found
        '500':
          description: Internal Server Error
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  error:
                    type: string
                    example: Internal Server Error
```

11.1.13 Tripdata – CMR

```
openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
- url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /tripdata/cmr/{companyIdentifier}/{tripId}:
    get:
      summary: Get CMR data
      parameters:
```

```
- name: companyIdentifier
  in: path
  required: true
  schema:
    type: string
- name: tripId
  in: path
  required: true
  schema:
    type: string
responses:
  '200':
    description: OK
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            # Logistic Operator
            companyIdentifier:
              type: string
            tripId:
              type: string
            departureDateTime:
              type: string
              format: date-time
            realDepartureDateTime:
              type: string
              format: date-time
            estimatedDateTimeOfArrival:
              type: string
              format: date-time
            realArrivalDateTime:
              type: string
              format: date-time
            document:
              type: array
              items:
                type: object
                properties:
                  referenceCode:
                    type: string
                  report:
                    type: object
                    format: application/pdf
                  sender:
                    type: object
                    properties:
                      name:
                        type: string
                      countryCode:
                        type: string
                      VAT:
                        type: string
                      address:
                        type: string
                  receiver:
                    type: object
```

```

    properties:
      name:
        type: string
      countryCode:
        type: string
      VAT:
        type: string
      address:
        type: string
  load:
    type: object
    properties:
      load_type:
        type: string
      load_description:
        type: string
      weight:
        type: number
        format: float
      umWeight:
        type: string
      size:
        type: object
        properties:
          type:
            type: string
          description:
            type: string
          width:
            type: number
            format: float
          height:
            type: number
            format: float
          depth:
            type: number
            format: float
          unitary:
            type: boolean
          um:
            type: string
'500':
  description: Internal Server Error
'404':
  description: CMR data not found

```

11.1.14 Tripdata – Current trip

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:

```

```

/tripdata/trip/{driverIdentifier}:
  get:
    summary: Get current trip data
    parameters:
      - name: driverIdentifier
        in: path
        required: true
        schema:
          type: string
      - name: countryCode
        in: query
        required: false
        schema:
          type: string
      - name: plateNumber
        in: query
        required: false
        schema:
          type: string
    responses:
      '200':
        description: OK
        content:
          application/json:
            schema:
              type: object
              properties:
                driverIdentifier:
                  type: string
                items:
                  type: array
                  items:
                    type: object
                    properties:
                      tripId:
                        type: string
                      referenceCode:
                        type: string
                      senderName:
                        type: string
                      receiverName:
                        type: string
                      goodsType:
                        type: string
                      goodsDescription:
                        type: string
                      estimatedTimeOfArrival:
                        type: string
                        format: date-time

```

11.1.15 Tripdata – ETA

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:

```

```

title: KEYSTONE REST Services
version: 6.1.0
servers:
- url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /tripdata/eta/{companyIdentifier}/{tripId}:
    get:
      summary: Get eta
      parameters:
        - name: companyIdentifier
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
        - name: tripId
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
      responses:
        '200':
          description: OK
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  companyIdentifier:
                    type: string
                  tripId:
                    type: string
                  estimatedTimeOfArrival:
                    type: string
                    format: datetime
        '500':
          description: Internal Server Error
        '404':
          description: ETA data not found

```

11.1.16 Tripdata – Phases

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
- url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /tripdata/phases/{companyIdentifier}/{tripId}:
    get:
      summary: Get all phases
      parameters:
        - name: companyIdentifier
          in: path
          required: true

```

```

    schema:
      type: string
  - name: tripId
    in: path
    required: true
    schema:
      type: string
responses:
  '200':
    description: OK
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            companyIdentifier:
              type: string
            tripId:
              type: string
            phases:
              type: array
              items:
                type: object
                properties:
                  dateTime:
                    type: string
                    format: date-time
                  status:
                    type: string
                  location:
                    type: object
                    properties:
                      type:
                        type: string
                      description:
                        type: string
                      internationalCode:
                        type: string
                      longitude:
                        type: string
                      latitude:
                        type: string
  '500':
    description: Internal Server Error
  '404':
    description: Phases data not found

```

11.1.17 Tripdata – Trips

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest

```

```

paths:
  /tripdata/trip/{companyIdentifier}/all:
    get:
      summary: Get trips data
      parameters:
        - name: companyIdentifier
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
            example: ALL_LOGISTIC_OPERATORS
          description: |
            Identifier of the company. Use "ALL_LOGISTIC_OPERATORS" to retrieve
data from all logistic operators.
        - name: locationInternationalCode
          in: query
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
      responses:
        '200':
          description: OK
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  companyIdentifier:
                    type: string
                    example: ALL_LOGISTIC_OPERATORS
                  tripData:
                    type: array
                    items:
                      type: object
                      properties:
                        tripId:
                          type: string
                        logisticOperator:
                          type: string
                          description: Name of the logistic operator (only present
when querying all operators)
                        referenceCode:
                          type: string
                        senderName:
                          type: string
                        receiverName:
                          type: string
                        goodsType:
                          type: string
                        goodsDescription:
                          type: string
                        estimatedTimeOfArrival:
                          type: string
                          format: date-time
        '404':
          description: Trips not found
        '500':
          description: Internal Server Error

```

11.1.18 Tripdata – Trips Arriving at Location within

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /tripdata/trip/scheduled/{locationInternationalCode}:
    get:
      summary: Get trips data scheduled to arrive at location within number of
hours
      parameters:
        - name: locationInternationalCode
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
        - name: within
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:
            oneOf:
              - type: integer
                description: Number of hours
              - type: string
                enum:
                  - DAY
                description: Represents the whole day until midnight
        - name: useInternationalLocationCode
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:
            type: boolean
            default: true
          description: If false, accepts an internal code for the location
        - name: withMostRecentPhase
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:
            type: boolean
            default: false
          description: If true, returns in addition the most recent phase of the
trips
        - name: isDestination
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:
            type: boolean
            default: true
          description: |
            If true (default), the locationInternationalCode identifies the
destination.

```

```

    If false, it identifies the origin.
responses:
  '200':
    description: OK
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            tripsPerCompany:
              type: array
              items:
                type: object
                properties:
                  companyIdentifier:
                    type: string
                  trips:
                    type: array
                    items:
                      type: object
                      properties:
                        tripId:
                          type: string
                        referenceCode:
                          type: string
                        senderName:
                          type: string
                        receiverName:
                          type: string
                        goodsType:
                          type: string
                        goodsDescription:
                          type: string
                        estimatedTimeOfArrival:
                          type: string
                          format: date-time
                        plateNumberCountryCode:
                          type: string
                          description: Country code of the vehicle
                        plateNumber:
                          type: string
                          description: Plate number of the vehicle
                        companyName:
                          type: string
                          description: Transport operator
                        companyFiscalCode:
                          type: string
                          description: Transport operator
                        phase:
                          type: object
                          properties:
                            dateTime:
                              type: string
                              format: date-time
                            status:
                              type: string
                            location:
                              type: object

```

```

        properties:
          type:
            type: string
          description:
            type: string
          locationCode:
            type: string
          longitude:
            type: string
          latitude:
            type: string
    '500':
      description: Internal Server Error
    '404':
      description: Trips not found

```

11.1.19 Tripdata – Trips Authorised at Gate

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /tripdata/trip/authorized/{locationInternationalCode}:
    get:
      summary: Get trips data authorized at gate
      parameters:
        - name: locationInternationalCode
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
        - name: gate #if gate is null, the service returns all trips data
          in: query
          required: false
          schema:
            type: string
      responses:
        '200':
          description: OK
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  tripsPerCompany:
                    type: array
                    items:
                      type: object
                      properties:
                        companyIdentifier:
                          type: string

```

```

trips:
  type: array
  items:
    type: object
    properties:
      tripId:
        type: string
      referenceCode:
        type: string
      senderName:
        type: string
      receiverName:
        type: string
      goodsType:
        type: string
      goodsDescription:
        type: string
      estimatedTimeOfArrival:
        type: string
        format: date-time
'500':
  description: Internal Server Error
'404':
  description: Trips not found

```

11.1.20 Truckdata – Insurance

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /truckdata/insurance/{countrycode}/{platenumber}:
    get:
      summary: Get the truck insurance data
      parameters:
        - name: countrycode
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
        - name: platenumber
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
      responses:
        '200':
          description: Success
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object

```

```

    properties:
      countryCode:
        type: string
      plateNumber:
        type: string
      isInsured:
        type: boolean
      activationDate:
        type: string
        format: date
      expirationDate:
        type: string
        format: date
      companyName:
        type: string
      insuranceNumber:
        type: string
  '404':
    description: Plate Number Not Found
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            error:
              type: string
              example: Plate number not found
  '500':
    description: Internal Server Error
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            error:
              type: string
              example: Internal Server Error

```

11.1.21 Truckdata – Owner

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /truckdata/owner/{countrycode}/{platenumber}:
    get:
      summary: Get the truck owner data
      parameters:
        - name: countrycode
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string

```

```

- name: platenumber
  in: path
  required: true
  schema:
    type: string
responses:
  '200':
    description: Success
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            countryCode:
              type: string
            plateNumber:
              type: string
            owner:
              type: object
              properties:
                companyName:
                  type: string
                companyFiscalCode:
                  type: string
  '404':
    description: Plate Number Not Found
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            error:
              type: string
            example: Plate number not found
  '500':
    description: Internal Server Error
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            error:
              type: string
            example: Internal Server Error

```

11.1.22 Truckdata – Technical Inspections

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /truckdata/technicalinspectionervice/{countrycode}/{platenumber}:

```

```
get:
  summary: Get the truck inspection data
  parameters:
    - name: countrycode
      in: path
      required: true
      schema:
        type: string
    - name: platenumber
      in: path
      required: true
      schema:
        type: string
  responses:
    '200':
      description: Success
      content:
        application/json:
          schema:
            type: object
            properties:
              countryCode:
                type: string
              plateNumber:
                type: string
              datesList:
                type: array
                items:
                  type: object
                  properties:
                    companyName:
                      type: string
                    technicalInspectionExecutionDate:
                      type: string
                      format: date
                    technicalInspectionOpeningDate:
                      type: string
                      format: date
                    technicalInspectionClosingDate:
                      type: string
                      format: date
                    isDone:
                      type: boolean
    '404':
      description: Plate Number Not Found
      content:
        application/json:
          schema:
            type: object
            properties:
              error:
                type: string
                example: Plate number not found
    '500':
      description: Internal Server Error
      content:
        application/json:
          schema:
```

```

type: object
properties:
  error:
    type: string
    example: Internal Server Error

```

11.1.23 Unloading Data – Gate

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
paths:
  /unloadingdata/gate/{companyIdentifier}/{tripId}:
    get:
      summary: Get unloading data per trip
      parameters:
        - name: companyIdentifier
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
        - name: tripId
          in: path
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
      responses:
        '200':
          description: OK
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  companyIdentifier:
                    type: string
                  tripId:
                    type: string
                  estimatedUnloadingTime:
                    type: string
                    format: date-time
                  gate:
                    type: object
                    properties:
                      description:
                        type: string
                        description: Description of the gate
                      latitude:
                        type: number
                        description: gate latitude
                        format: float
                        example: '39.4325962'

```

```

        longitude:
          type: number
          description: gate longitude
          format: float
          example: '9.5624146'
'500':
  description: Internal Server Error
'404':
  description: Gate data not found

```

11.1.24 Unloading Data – Queue at Gate

```

openapi: 3.0.0
info:
  title: KEYSTONE REST Services
  version: 6.1.0
servers:
  - url: https://www.keystone-project.com/rest
    description: Keystone REST API Server
paths:
  /unloadingdata/queue/all:
    get:
      summary: Number of trucks per gate
      parameters:
        - name: locationInternationalCode
          in: query
          required: true
          schema:
            type: string
      responses:
        "200":
          description: Success
          content:
            application/json:
              schema:
                type: object
                properties:
                  trucksPerGate:
                    type: array
                    items:
                      type: object
                      properties:
                        gate:
                          type: string
                          description: The gate number
                        trucksAtGate:
                          type: integer
                          description: The number of trucks at the gate
          example:
            trucksPerGate:
              - gate: "A1"
                trucksAtGate: 5
              - gate: "B2"
                trucksAtGate: 3
        "404":

```

```
description: Number of trucks per gate service not found
content:
  application/json:
    schema:
      type: object
      properties:
        error:
          type: string
          example: "Truck summary not found"
"500":
  description: Internal Server Error
  content:
    application/json:
      schema:
        type: object
        properties:
          error:
            type: string
            example: "Internal Server Error"
```

12. Annex D – DB generation scripts

12.1 KEYSTONE Databases Generation Scripts

In the following sections the KEYSTONE generation scripts are reported in detail in SQL format for MySQL.

12.1.1 Keystone Database

```

CREATE DATABASE IF NOT EXISTS `keystone` /*!40100 DEFAULT CHARACTER SET utf8mb4
COLLATE utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci */ /*!80016 DEFAULT ENCRYPTION='N' */;
USE `keystone`;
-- MySQL dump 10.13  Distrib 8.0.40, for Win64 (x86_64)
--
-- Host: 127.0.0.1    Database: keystone
-- -----
-- Server version 8.0.32

/*!40101 SET @OLD_CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT=@@CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS=@@CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_COLLATION_CONNECTION=@@COLLATION_CONNECTION */;
/*!50503 SET NAMES utf8 */;
/*!40103 SET @OLD_TIME_ZONE=@@TIME_ZONE */;
/*!40103 SET TIME_ZONE='+00:00' */;
/*!40014 SET @OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS=@@UNIQUE_CHECKS, UNIQUE_CHECKS=0 */;
/*!40014 SET @OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@@FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS, FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=0 */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_SQL_MODE=@@SQL_MODE, SQL_MODE='NO_AUTO_VALUE_ON_ZERO' */;
/*!40111 SET @OLD_SQL_NOTES=@@SQL_NOTES, SQL_NOTES=0 */;

--
-- Table structure for table `category`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `category`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `category` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type`
enum('AM', 'A', 'A1', 'A2', 'B', 'BE', 'B1', 'C1', 'C1E', 'C', 'CE', 'D1', 'D1E', 'D', 'DE')
DEFAULT NULL,
  `description` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `issue_date` date DEFAULT NULL,
  `expiry_date` date DEFAULT NULL,
  `status`
enum('VALID', 'EXPIRED', 'SUSPENDED', 'REVOKED', 'CONFISCATED', 'LOST/STOLEN') DEFAULT
NULL,
  `code_95` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `category`
--

```

```

LOCK TABLES `category` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `category` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `category` VALUES (1,'C','Heavy Truck License','2020-01-01','2030-01-01','VALID','YES'),(2,'B','Car License','2018-01-01','2028-01-01','VALID',NULL);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `category` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `coordinates`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `coordinates`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `coordinates` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `latitude` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `longitude` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `coordinates`
--

LOCK TABLES `coordinates` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `coordinates` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `coordinates` VALUES (1,'40.7128','-74.0060'),(2,'51.5074','-0.1278');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `coordinates` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `departure_and_arrival`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `departure_and_arrival`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `departure_and_arrival` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `departure_date_time` datetime DEFAULT NULL,
  `real_departure_date_time` datetime DEFAULT NULL,
  `estimated_date_time_of_arrival` datetime DEFAULT NULL,
  `real_arrival_date_time` datetime DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=2 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `departure_and_arrival`
--

LOCK TABLES `departure_and_arrival` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `departure_and_arrival` DISABLE KEYS */;

```

```

INSERT INTO `departure_and_arrival` VALUES (1,'2025-06-11 03:57:58','2025-06-11
04:57:58','2025-06-11 11:57:58',NULL);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `departure_and_arrival` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `driver`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `driver`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `driver` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `first_name` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `last_name` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `country_code` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `vat` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `licence_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `licence_id` (`licence_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `driver_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`licence_id`) REFERENCES `licence` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `driver`
--

LOCK TABLES `driver` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `driver` VALUES
(1,'Alice','Smith','IT','RSSMRA80A01H501R',1),(2,'Bob','Jones','IT','BNCGNN75B02L21
9K',2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `driving_interval`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `driving_interval`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `driving_interval` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `start_date_time` datetime DEFAULT NULL,
  `end_date_time` datetime DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `driving_interval`
--

```

```

LOCK TABLES `driving_interval` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driving_interval` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `driving_interval` VALUES (1,'2025-06-11 06:57:58','2025-06-11
08:57:58'),(2,'2025-06-11 04:57:58','2025-06-11 07:57:58');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driving_interval` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `driving_interval_exceeding`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `driving_interval_exceeding`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `driving_interval_exceeding` (
  `interval_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  `etl_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`interval_id`,`etl_id`),
  KEY `etl_id` (`etl_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `driving_interval_exceeding_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`interval_id`)
REFERENCES `driving_interval` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `driving_interval_exceeding_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`etl_id`) REFERENCES
`exceeding_time_limits` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `driving_interval_exceeding`
--

LOCK TABLES `driving_interval_exceeding` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driving_interval_exceeding` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `driving_interval_exceeding` VALUES (1,1),(2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driving_interval_exceeding` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `exceeding_time_limits`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `exceeding_time_limits`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `exceeding_time_limits` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `hours` int DEFAULT NULL,
  `minutes` int DEFAULT NULL,
  `seconds` int DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `exceeding_time_limits`
--

```

```

LOCK TABLES `exceeding_time_limits` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `exceeding_time_limits` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `exceeding_time_limits` VALUES
(1,'DrivingTimeExceeded',10,15,30),(2,'BreakTooShort',1,5,0);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `exceeding_time_limits` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `geolocation`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `geolocation`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `geolocation` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `date_time` datetime NOT NULL,
  `coordinates_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `coordinates_id` (`coordinates_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `geolocation_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`coordinates_id`) REFERENCES
`coordinates` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `geolocation`
--

LOCK TABLES `geolocation` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `geolocation` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `geolocation` VALUES (1,'2025-06-11 09:57:58',1),(2,'2025-06-11
09:57:58',2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `geolocation` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `insurance`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `insurance`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `insurance` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `name` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `number` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `is_insured` tinyint(1) DEFAULT NULL,
  `activation_date` date DEFAULT NULL,
  `expiration_date` date DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `insurance`

```

```
--
LOCK TABLES `insurance` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `insurance` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `insurance` VALUES (1,'AllSecure','INS123',1,'2024-01-01','2025-01-01'),(2,'DriveSafe','INS456',0,'2023-05-10','2024-05-10');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `insurance` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `licence`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `licence`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `licence` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `country_code` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `licence`
--

LOCK TABLES `licence` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `licence` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `licence` VALUES (1,'US'),(2,'UK');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `licence` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `licence_category`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `licence_category`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `licence_category` (
  `licence_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  `category_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`licence_id`,`category_id`),
  KEY `category_id` (`category_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `licence_category_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`licence_id`) REFERENCES
`licence` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `licence_category_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`category_id`) REFERENCES
`category` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `licence_category`
--

LOCK TABLES `licence_category` WRITE;
```

```

/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `licence_category` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `licence_category` VALUES (1,1),(2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `licence_category` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `load_size`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `load_size`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `load_size` (
  `load_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  `size_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`load_id`,`size_id`),
  KEY `size_id` (`size_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `load_size_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`load_id`) REFERENCES `loading`
(`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `load_size_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`size_id`) REFERENCES `size` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `load_size`
--

LOCK TABLES `load_size` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `load_size` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `load_size` VALUES (1,1),(2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `load_size` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `loading`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `loading`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `loading` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `description` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `weight` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `loading`
--

LOCK TABLES `loading` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `loading` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `loading` VALUES (1,'Freight','Office
supplies',500),(2,'Goods','Construction material',1500);

```

```

/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `loading` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `location`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `location`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `location` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `description` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `coordinates_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `type` enum('GENERIC','GATE','TERMINAL','PORT','AIRPORT','STATION') DEFAULT NULL,
  `international_code` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `coordinates_id` (`coordinates_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `location_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`coordinates_id`) REFERENCES
`coordinates` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `location`
--

LOCK TABLES `location` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `location` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `location` VALUES (1,'Main Terminal',1,'TERMINAL','MT01'),(2,'Central
Port',2,'PORT','CP02');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `location` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `organization`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `organization`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `organization` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `name` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `country_code` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `vat` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `address` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `type` enum('CUSTOMER','OPERATOR') DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `organization`
--

```

```

LOCK TABLES `organization` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `organization` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `organization` VALUES (1,'LogiCorp','US','VAT001','123 Main St,
NY','CUSTOMER'),(2,'FastOps','UK','VAT002','456 Queen Rd, London','OPERATOR');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `organization` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `owner`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `owner`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `owner` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `name` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `vat` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `owner`
--

LOCK TABLES `owner` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `owner` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `owner` VALUES (1,'John Transport Inc.','VAT12345'),(2,'Speedy Haulers
Ltd.','VAT67890');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `owner` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `payload`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `payload`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `payload` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `payload`
--

LOCK TABLES `payload` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `payload` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `payload` VALUES (1),(2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `payload` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

```

```
--
-- Table structure for table `phase`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `phase`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `phase` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `location_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `starting_time` datetime DEFAULT NULL,
  `status` enum('PLANNING','IN_PROGRESS','CHECKED_IN','ARRIVED AT PICKUP','ARRIVED
AT
DESTINATION','LOADING','UNLOADING','IN_TRANSIT','COMPLETED','DELAYED','CANCELED')
DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `location_id` (`location_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `phase_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`location_id`) REFERENCES `location`
(`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `phase`
--

LOCK TABLES `phase` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `phase` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `phase` VALUES (1,1,'2025-06-11 06:57:58','IN_TRANSIT'),(2,2,'2025-06-
11 08:57:58','ARRIVED AT DESTINATION');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `phase` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `phase_payload`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `phase_payload`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `phase_payload` (
  `phase_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  `payload_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`phase_id`,`payload_id`),
  KEY `payload_id` (`payload_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `phase_payload_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`phase_id`) REFERENCES `phase`
(`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `phase_payload_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`payload_id`) REFERENCES `payload`
(`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `phase_payload`
--

LOCK TABLES `phase_payload` WRITE;
```

```

/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `phase_payload` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `phase_payload` VALUES (1,1),(2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `phase_payload` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `size`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `size`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `size` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `description` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `width` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `height` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `depth` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `unitary` tinyint(1) DEFAULT NULL,
  `um` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `size`
--

LOCK TABLES `size` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `size` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `size` VALUES (1,'Box','Standard Box',100,50,60,1,'cm'),(2,'Pallet','EU
Pallet',120,80,100,0,'cm');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `size` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `tachograph_card`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `tachograph_card`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `tachograph_card` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `driver_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `driver_id` (`driver_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `tachograph_card_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`driver_id`) REFERENCES `driver`
(`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `tachograph_card`
--

```

```

LOCK TABLES `tachograph_card` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `tachograph_card` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `tachograph_card` VALUES (1,1),(2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `tachograph_card` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `tachograph_card_driving_interval`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `tachograph_card_driving_interval`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `tachograph_card_driving_interval` (
  `card_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  `interval_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`card_id`,`interval_id`),
  KEY `interval_id` (`interval_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `tachograph_card_driving_interval_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`card_id`)
REFERENCES `tachograph_card` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `tachograph_card_driving_interval_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`interval_id`)
REFERENCES `driving_interval` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `tachograph_card_driving_interval`
--

LOCK TABLES `tachograph_card_driving_interval` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `tachograph_card_driving_interval` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `tachograph_card_driving_interval` VALUES (1,1),(2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `tachograph_card_driving_interval` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `technical_inspection`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `technical_inspection`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `technical_inspection` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `company` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `technical_inspection_number` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `execution_date` date DEFAULT NULL,
  `expiration_date` date DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `technical_inspection`
--

```

```
LOCK TABLES `technical_inspection` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `technical_inspection` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `technical_inspection` VALUES (1,'TechInspect Ltd.','TI001','2024-01-15','2025-01-15'),(2,'CheckAuto','TI002','2023-06-20','2024-06-20');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `technical_inspection` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
--
-- Table structure for table `traffic_violation`
--
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `traffic_violation`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `traffic_violation` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `description` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `code` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `country_code` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `fine` decimal(10,2) DEFAULT NULL,
  `payment_due_date` date DEFAULT NULL,
  `payment_date` date DEFAULT NULL,
  `is_paid` tinyint(1) DEFAULT NULL,
  `validity_points` int DEFAULT NULL,
  `driver_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `driver_id` (`driver_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `traffic_violation_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`driver_id`) REFERENCES `driver` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;
```

```
--
-- Dumping data for table `traffic_violation`
--
```

```
LOCK TABLES `traffic_violation` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `traffic_violation` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `traffic_violation` VALUES (1,'Speeding','SPD01','US',200.00,'2025-07-01',NULL,0,3,1),(2,'Running red light','RED02','UK',150.00,'2025-08-15','2025-08-01',1,2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `traffic_violation` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
--
-- Table structure for table `traffic_violation_payload`
--
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `traffic_violation_payload`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `traffic_violation_payload` (
  `violation_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  `payload_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`violation_id`,`payload_id`),
  KEY `payload_id` (`payload_id`),
```

```

    CONSTRAINT `traffic_violation_payload_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`violation_id`)
REFERENCES `traffic_violation` (`id`),
    CONSTRAINT `traffic_violation_payload_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`payload_id`)
REFERENCES `payload` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `traffic_violation_payload`
--

LOCK TABLES `traffic_violation_payload` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `traffic_violation_payload` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `traffic_violation_payload` VALUES (1,1), (2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `traffic_violation_payload` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `transport_operation`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `transport_operation`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `transport_operation` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `logistic_operator_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `departure_and_arrival_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `driver_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `vehicle_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `logistic_operator_id` (`logistic_operator_id`),
  KEY `departure_and_arrival_id` (`departure_and_arrival_id`),
  KEY `driver_id` (`driver_id`),
  KEY `vehicle_id` (`vehicle_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transport_operation_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`logistic_operator_id`)
REFERENCES `organization` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transport_operation_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`departure_and_arrival_id`)
REFERENCES `departure_and_arrival` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transport_operation_ibfk_3` FOREIGN KEY (`driver_id`) REFERENCES
`driver` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transport_operation_ibfk_4` FOREIGN KEY (`vehicle_id`) REFERENCES
`vehicle` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `transport_operation`
--

LOCK TABLES `transport_operation` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `transport_operation` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `transport_operation` VALUES (1,1,1,1,1), (2,2,1,2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `transport_operation` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--

```

```
-- Table structure for table `transport_operation_payload`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `transport_operation_payload`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `transport_operation_payload` (
  `transport_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  `payload_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`transport_id`,`payload_id`),
  KEY `payload_id` (`payload_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transport_operation_payload_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`transport_id`)
REFERENCES `transport_operation` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transport_operation_payload_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`payload_id`)
REFERENCES `payload` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `transport_operation_payload`
--

LOCK TABLES `transport_operation_payload` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `transport_operation_payload` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `transport_operation_payload` VALUES (1,1), (2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `transport_operation_payload` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `transport_operation_phase`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `transport_operation_phase`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `transport_operation_phase` (
  `transport_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  `phase_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`transport_id`,`phase_id`),
  KEY `phase_id` (`phase_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transport_operation_phase_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`transport_id`)
REFERENCES `transport_operation` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transport_operation_phase_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`phase_id`) REFERENCES
`phase` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `transport_operation_phase`
--

LOCK TABLES `transport_operation_phase` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `transport_operation_phase` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `transport_operation_phase` VALUES (1,1), (2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `transport_operation_phase` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
```

```
-- Table structure for table `transport_operation_tdd`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `transport_operation_tdd`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `transport_operation_tdd` (
  `transport_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  `tdd_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`transport_id`,`tdd_id`),
  KEY `tdd_id` (`tdd_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transport_operation_tdd_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`transport_id`)
REFERENCES `transport_operation` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transport_operation_tdd_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`tdd_id`) REFERENCES
`transportation_document_data` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `transport_operation_tdd`
--

LOCK TABLES `transport_operation_tdd` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `transport_operation_tdd` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `transport_operation_tdd` VALUES (1,1),(2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `transport_operation_tdd` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `transportation_document_data`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `transportation_document_data`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `transportation_document_data` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `reference` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `sender_organization_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `receiver_organization_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `starting_point_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `ending_point_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `load_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  `document` longblob,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `sender_organization_id` (`sender_organization_id`),
  KEY `receiver_organization_id` (`receiver_organization_id`),
  KEY `starting_point_id` (`starting_point_id`),
  KEY `ending_point_id` (`ending_point_id`),
  KEY `load_id` (`load_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transportation_document_data_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY
(`sender_organization_id`) REFERENCES `organization` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transportation_document_data_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY
(`receiver_organization_id`) REFERENCES `organization` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transportation_document_data_ibfk_3` FOREIGN KEY
(`starting_point_id`) REFERENCES `location` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `transportation_document_data_ibfk_4` FOREIGN KEY (`ending_point_id`)
REFERENCES `location` (`id`),
```

```

    CONSTRAINT `transportation_document_data_ibfk_5` FOREIGN KEY (`load_id`)
REFERENCES `loading` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `transportation_document_data`
--

LOCK TABLES `transportation_document_data` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `transportation_document_data` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `transportation_document_data` VALUES
(1, 'DOC001', 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, NULL), (2, 'DOC002', 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, NULL);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `transportation_document_data` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `vehicle`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `vehicle`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `vehicle` (
  `id` bigint NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `plate_number` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `country_code` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `type` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `model` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `owner_id` bigint DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `owner_id` (`owner_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `vehicle_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`owner_id`) REFERENCES `owner` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `vehicle`
--

LOCK TABLES `vehicle` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `vehicle` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `vehicle` VALUES (1, 'ABC123', 'IT', 'Truck', 'Volvo
FH', 1), (2, 'XYZ789', 'IT', 'Van', 'Ford Transit', 2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `vehicle` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `vehicle_geolocation`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `vehicle_geolocation`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `vehicle_geolocation` (
  `vehicle_id` bigint NOT NULL,

```

```

`geolocation_id` bigint NOT NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`vehicle_id`,`geolocation_id`),
KEY `geolocation_id` (`geolocation_id`),
CONSTRAINT `vehicle_geolocation_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`vehicle_id`) REFERENCES
`vehicle` (`id`),
CONSTRAINT `vehicle_geolocation_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`geolocation_id`) REFERENCES
`geolocation` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `vehicle_geolocation`
--

LOCK TABLES `vehicle_geolocation` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `vehicle_geolocation` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `vehicle_geolocation` VALUES (1,1),(2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `vehicle_geolocation` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `vehicle_insurance`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `vehicle_insurance`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `vehicle_insurance` (
  `vehicle_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  `insurance_id` bigint NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`vehicle_id`,`insurance_id`),
  KEY `insurance_id` (`insurance_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `vehicle_insurance_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`vehicle_id`) REFERENCES
`vehicle` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `vehicle_insurance_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY (`insurance_id`) REFERENCES
`insurance` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `vehicle_insurance`
--

LOCK TABLES `vehicle_insurance` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `vehicle_insurance` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `vehicle_insurance` VALUES (1,1),(2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `vehicle_insurance` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `vehicle_technical_inspection`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `vehicle_technical_inspection`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `vehicle_technical_inspection` (
  `vehicle_id` bigint NOT NULL,

```

```

`technical_inspection_id` bigint NOT NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`vehicle_id`,`technical_inspection_id`),
KEY `technical_inspection_id` (`technical_inspection_id`),
CONSTRAINT `vehicle_technical_inspection_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`vehicle_id`)
REFERENCES `vehicle` (`id`),
CONSTRAINT `vehicle_technical_inspection_ibfk_2` FOREIGN KEY
(`technical_inspection_id`) REFERENCES `technical_inspection` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

```

```

--
-- Dumping data for table `vehicle_technical_inspection`
--

```

```

LOCK TABLES `vehicle_technical_inspection` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `vehicle_technical_inspection` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `vehicle_technical_inspection` VALUES (1,1),(2,2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `vehicle_technical_inspection` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;
/*!40103 SET TIME_ZONE=@OLD_TIME_ZONE */;

/*!40101 SET SQL_MODE=@OLD_SQL_MODE */;
/*!40014 SET FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS */;
/*!40014 SET UNIQUE_CHECKS=@OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS */;
/*!40101 SET CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT=@OLD_CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT */;
/*!40101 SET CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS=@OLD_CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS */;
/*!40101 SET COLLATION_CONNECTION=@OLD_COLLATION_CONNECTION */;
/*!40111 SET SQL_NOTES=@OLD_SQL_NOTES */;

```

12.1.2 Keystone Authentication Database

```

CREATE DATABASE IF NOT EXISTS `keystone_auth` /*!40100 DEFAULT CHARACTER SET
utf8mb4 COLLATE utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci */ /*!80016 DEFAULT ENCRYPTION='N' */;
USE `keystone_auth`;
-- MySQL dump 10.13  Distrib 8.0.40, for Win64 (x86_64)
--
-- Host: 127.0.0.1    Database: keystone_auth
--
-----
-- Server version 8.0.32

/*!40101 SET @OLD_CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT=@@CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS=@@CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_COLLATION_CONNECTION=@@COLLATION_CONNECTION */;
/*!50503 SET NAMES utf8 */;
/*!40103 SET @OLD_TIME_ZONE=@@TIME_ZONE */;
/*!40103 SET TIME_ZONE='+00:00' */;
/*!40014 SET @OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS=@@UNIQUE_CHECKS, UNIQUE_CHECKS=0 */;
/*!40014 SET @OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@@FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS, FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=0 */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_SQL_MODE=@@SQL_MODE, SQL_MODE='NO_AUTO_VALUE_ON_ZERO' */;
/*!40111 SET @OLD_SQL_NOTES=@@SQL_NOTES, SQL_NOTES=0 */;

--
-- Table structure for table `Coordinates`
--

```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `Coordinates`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `Coordinates` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `latitude` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `longitude` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=6 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `Coordinates`
--

LOCK TABLES `Coordinates` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `Coordinates` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `Coordinates` VALUES (1,'45.4642 N','9.1900 E'),(2,'41.9028 N','12.4964
E'),(3,'37.5019 N','15.0921 E'),(4,'45.0703 N','7.6869 E'),(5,'39.2238 N','9.1217
E');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `Coordinates` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `Driver`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `Driver`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `Driver` (
  `id` int NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_driver_user` FOREIGN KEY (`id`) REFERENCES `User` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `Driver`
--

LOCK TABLES `Driver` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `Driver` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `Driver` VALUES (1),(2),(6);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `Driver` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `Location`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `Location`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `Location` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `description` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
```

```

`internationalCode` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL,
`id_coordinates` int DEFAULT NULL,
`id_location_type` int NOT NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
KEY `fk_location_coordinates` (`id_coordinates`),
KEY `fk_location_type` (`id_location_type`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_location_coordinates` FOREIGN KEY (`id_coordinates`) REFERENCES
`Coordinates` (`id`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_location_type` FOREIGN KEY (`id_location_type`) REFERENCES
`LocationType` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=7 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `Location`
--

LOCK TABLES `Location` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `Location` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `Location` VALUES (1,'Porto di Genova','ITGOA',NULL,1),(2,'Area
Metropolitana Milano Centro','ITMIL',1,2),(3,'Autostrada A1 - Casello Roma
Nord','ITRNA1',2,3),(4,'Porto di Catania','ITCTA',3,1),(5,'Interporto Quadrante
Europa, Verona','ITVRN',NULL,5),(6,'Valico del Brennero','ITBRE',NULL,4);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `Location` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `LocationType`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `LocationType`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `LocationType` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type_name` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=6 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `LocationType`
--

LOCK TABLES `LocationType` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `LocationType` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `LocationType` VALUES
(1,'PORT'),(2,'CITY'),(3,'HIGHWAY_SECTION'),(4,'BORDER_CROSSING'),(5,'WAREHOUSE');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `LocationType` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `PortAuthority`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `PortAuthority`;

```

```

/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `PortAuthority` (
  `id` int NOT NULL,
  `id_location` int NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `fk_portauthority_location` (`id_location`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_portauthority_location` FOREIGN KEY (`id_location`) REFERENCES
`Location` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_portauthority_user` FOREIGN KEY (`id`) REFERENCES `User` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

```

```

--
-- Dumping data for table `PortAuthority`
--

```

```

LOCK TABLES `PortAuthority` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `PortAuthority` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `PortAuthority` VALUES (4,1),(8,1),(5,4);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `PortAuthority` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

```

```

--
-- Table structure for table `RoadPolice`
--

```

```

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `RoadPolice`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `RoadPolice` (
  `id` int NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_roadpolice_user` FOREIGN KEY (`id`) REFERENCES `User` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

```

```

--
-- Dumping data for table `RoadPolice`
--

```

```

LOCK TABLES `RoadPolice` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `RoadPolice` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `RoadPolice` VALUES (3),(7);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `RoadPolice` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

```

```

--
-- Table structure for table `Role`
--

```

```

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `Role`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `Role` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `description` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)

```

```

) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=4 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `Role`
--

LOCK TABLES `Role` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `Role` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `Role` VALUES (1,'DRIVER'), (2,'PORTAUTHORITY'), (3,'ROADPOLICE');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `Role` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `User`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `User`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `User` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `firstName` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `lastName` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `countryCode` varchar(10) DEFAULT NULL,
  `vat` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL,
  `user_name` varchar(100) NOT NULL,
  `password` varchar(255) NOT NULL,
  `user_type` varchar(20) NOT NULL,
  `id_role` int NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  UNIQUE KEY `user_name` (`user_name`),
  KEY `fk_user_role` (`id_role`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_user_role` FOREIGN KEY (`id_role`) REFERENCES `Role` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=9 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `User`
--

LOCK TABLES `User` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `User` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `User` VALUES
(1,'Mario','Rossi','IT','RSSMRA80A01H501A','mario.rossi','password','Driver',1), (2,
'Luigi','Verdi','IT','VRDLGU85B02F205Z','luigi.verdi','password','Driver',1), (3,'Gi
ulia','Bianchi','IT','BNCGLI90C03A944X','giulia.bianchi','password','RoadPolice',3)
, (4,'Antonio','Gialli','IT','GLLANT75D04L219Y','antonio.gialli','password','PortAut
hority',2), (5,'Laura','Neri','IT','NRELRA88E05H501W','laura.neri','password','PortA
uthority',2), (6,'Paolo','Bruni','FR','BRNPLA70S15Z110X','paolo.bruni','password','D
river',1), (7,'Stefania','Costa','IT','CSTSFI82M41H501K','stefania.costa','password
','RoadPolice',3), (8,'Marco','Esposito','IT','SPSMRC78B21F839P','marco.esposito','pa
ssword','PortAuthority',2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `User` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;
/*!40103 SET TIME_ZONE=@OLD_TIME_ZONE */;

```

```

/*!40101 SET SQL_MODE=@OLD_SQL_MODE */;
/*!40014 SET FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS */;
/*!40014 SET UNIQUE_CHECKS=@OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS */;
/*!40101 SET CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT=@OLD_CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT */;
/*!40101 SET CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS=@OLD_CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS */;
/*!40101 SET COLLATION_CONNECTION=@OLD_COLLATION_CONNECTION */;
/*!40111 SET SQL_NOTES=@OLD_SQL_NOTES */;

```

12.1.3 Keystone Gateway Database

```

CREATE DATABASE IF NOT EXISTS `keystone_gateway` /*!40100 DEFAULT CHARACTER SET
utf8mb4 COLLATE utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci */ /*!80016 DEFAULT ENCRYPTION='N' */;
USE `keystone_gateway`;
-- MySQL dump 10.13  Distrib 8.0.40, for Win64 (x86_64)
--
-- Host: 127.0.0.1    Database: keystone_gateway
-- -----
-- Server version 8.0.32

/*!40101 SET @OLD_CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT=@@CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS=@@CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_COLLATION_CONNECTION=@@COLLATION_CONNECTION */;
/*!50503 SET NAMES utf8 */;
/*!40103 SET @OLD_TIME_ZONE=@@TIME_ZONE */;
/*!40103 SET TIME_ZONE='+00:00' */;
/*!40014 SET @OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS=@@UNIQUE_CHECKS, UNIQUE_CHECKS=0 */;
/*!40014 SET @OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@@FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS, FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=0 */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_SQL_MODE=@@SQL_MODE, SQL_MODE='NO_AUTO_VALUE_ON_ZERO' */;
/*!40111 SET @OLD_SQL_NOTES=@@SQL_NOTES, SQL_NOTES=0 */;

--
-- Table structure for table `adapter_config`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `adapter_config`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `adapter_config` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `resource_path` varchar(255) NOT NULL,
  `external_system` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `adapter_uri` varchar(255) NOT NULL,
  `http_method` varchar(10) NOT NULL,
  `request_body_id` int DEFAULT NULL,
  `active` tinyint DEFAULT '1',
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `fk_adapter_config_request_template` (`request_body_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_adapter_config_request_template` FOREIGN KEY (`request_body_id`)
REFERENCES `request_template` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=11 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

```

```
--
```

```
-- Dumping data for table `adapter_config`
--

LOCK TABLES `adapter_config` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `adapter_config` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `adapter_config` VALUES (1,'/company','db-
adapter','http://localhost:8084/v1/company','GET',NULL,1),(2,'/terminal','db-
adapter','http://localhost:8084/v1/terminal','GET',NULL,1),(3,'/v1/vehicles/{countryCode}/{plateNumber}/revisions','movehub-
adapter','http://localhost:8085/v1/vehicles/{countryCode}/{plateNumber}/revisions',
'GET',NULL,1),(4,'/v1/vehicles/{countryCode}/{plateNumber}/owners','movehub-
adapter','http://localhost:8085/v1/vehicles/{countryCode}/{plateNumber}/owners','GE
T',NULL,1),(5,'/v1/vehicles/{countryCode}/{plateNumber}/insurances','movehub-
adapter','http://localhost:8085/v1/vehicles/{countryCode}/{plateNumber}/insurances'
,'GET',NULL,1),(6,'/v1/transport-operations','db-
adapter','http://localhost:8084/v1/transport-
operations','GET',NULL,1),(7,'/v1/drivers/{countryCode}/{vat}/licenses','movehub-
adapter','http://localhost:8085/v1/drivers/{countryCode}/{vat}/licenses','GET',NULL
,1),(8,'/v1/drivers/{countryCode}/{vat}','movehub-
adapter','http://localhost:8085/v1/drivers/{countryCode}/{vat}','GET',NULL,1),(9,'/
v1/drivers/{countryCode}/{vat}/tachograph-cards','movehub-
adapter','http://localhost:8085/v1/drivers/{countryCode}/{vat}/tachograph-
cards','GET',NULL,1),(10,'/v1/drivers/{countryCode}/{vat}/traffic-
violations','movehub-
adapter','http://localhost:8085/v1/drivers/{countryCode}/{vat}/traffic-
violations','GET',NULL,1);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `adapter_config` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `request_template`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `request_template`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `request_template` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `request_body` text,
  `active` tinyint DEFAULT '1',
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4 COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `request_template`
--

LOCK TABLES `request_template` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `request_template` DISABLE KEYS */;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `request_template` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;
/*!40103 SET TIME_ZONE=@OLD_TIME_ZONE */;

/*!40101 SET SQL_MODE=@OLD_SQL_MODE */;
/*!40014 SET FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS */;
/*!40014 SET UNIQUE_CHECKS=@OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS */;
/*!40101 SET CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT=@OLD_CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT */;
```

```

/*!40101 SET CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS=@OLD_CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS */;
/*!40101 SET COLLATION_CONNECTION=@OLD_COLLATION_CONNECTION */;
/*!40111 SET SQL_NOTES=@OLD_SQL_NOTES */;

```

12.1.4 Movehub Database

```

CREATE DATABASE IF NOT EXISTS `movehub` /*!40100 DEFAULT CHARACTER SET utf8mb4
COLLATE utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci */ /*!80016 DEFAULT ENCRYPTION='N' */;
USE `movehub`;
-- MySQL dump 10.13  Distrib 8.0.40, for Win64 (x86_64)
--
-- Host: 127.0.0.1    Database: movehub
-- -----
-- Server version 8.0.32

/*!40101 SET @OLD_CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT=@@CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS=@@CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_COLLATION_CONNECTION=@@COLLATION_CONNECTION */;
/*!50503 SET NAMES utf8 */;
/*!40103 SET @OLD_TIME_ZONE=@@TIME_ZONE */;
/*!40103 SET TIME_ZONE='+00:00' */;
/*!40014 SET @OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS=@@UNIQUE_CHECKS, UNIQUE_CHECKS=0 */;
/*!40014 SET @OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@@FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS, FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=0 */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_SQL_MODE=@@SQL_MODE, SQL_MODE='NO_AUTO_VALUE_ON_ZERO' */;
/*!40111 SET @OLD_SQL_NOTES=@@SQL_NOTES, SQL_NOTES=0 */;

--
-- Table structure for table `driver`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `driver`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `driver` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `fiscal_identifier` varchar(16) NOT NULL,
  `first_name` varchar(20) NOT NULL,
  `last_name` varchar(20) NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  UNIQUE KEY `fiscal_identifier` (`fiscal_identifier`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=6 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `driver`
--

LOCK TABLES `driver` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `driver` VALUES
(1, 'RSSMRA80A01H501R', 'Mario', 'Rossi'), (2, 'BNCGNN75B02L219K', 'Gianni', 'Bianchi'), (3, 'VRDGPP90C03F205X', 'Giovanni', 'Verdi'), (4, 'CRSLGT85D04Z123Y', 'Luigi', 'Carli'), (5, 'MRARNT70E05H612W', 'Antonio', 'Marra');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver` ENABLE KEYS */;

```

```

UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `driver_licence`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `driver_licence`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `driver_licence` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `country_code` varchar(5) NOT NULL,
  `driver_licence_identifier` varchar(16) NOT NULL,
  `end_validity_date` date NOT NULL,
  `driver_id` int NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  UNIQUE KEY `driver_licence_identifier` (`driver_licence_identifier`),
  UNIQUE KEY `driver_id` (`driver_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_driver_licence_driver` FOREIGN KEY (`driver_id`) REFERENCES
`driver` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=6 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `driver_licence`
--

LOCK TABLES `driver_licence` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver_licence` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `driver_licence` VALUES (1,'IT','ABCD123456789012','2025-12-
31',1),(2,'FR','XYZW987654321098','2024-06-30',2),(3,'DE','LMNO123456789012','2023-
09-15',3),(4,'ES','QRST987654321098','2026-03-
20',4),(5,'UK','UVWX123456789012','2027-01-10',5);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver_licence` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `driver_licence_category`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `driver_licence_category`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `driver_licence_category` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type_id` int NOT NULL,
  `driver_licence_id` int NOT NULL,
  `status_id` int NOT NULL,
  `start_validity_date` date NOT NULL,
  `code95` varchar(20) NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  UNIQUE KEY `code95` (`code95`),
  KEY `fk_type_driver_licence` (`type_id`),
  KEY `fk_status_driver_licence_category` (`status_id`),
  KEY `category_driver_licence_idx` (`driver_licence_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_category_driver_licence` FOREIGN KEY (`driver_licence_id`)
REFERENCES `driver_licence` (`id`),

```

```

    CONSTRAINT `fk_status_driver_licence_category` FOREIGN KEY (`status_id`)
REFERENCES `driver_licence_status` (`id`),
    CONSTRAINT `fk_type_driver_licence` FOREIGN KEY (`type_id`) REFERENCES
`driver_licence_category_type` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=8 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `driver_licence_category`
--

LOCK TABLES `driver_licence_category` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver_licence_category` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `driver_licence_category` VALUES (1,5,1,1,'2023-10-
15','CODE95_ABC123'), (2,6,1,1,'2023-10-15','CODE95_XYZ456'), (3,2,2,1,'2023-10-
15','CODE95_LMN789'), (4,3,2,2,'2023-10-15','CODE95_QRS012'), (5,8,3,3,'2023-10-
15','CODE95_TUV345'), (6,7,3,4,'2023-10-15','CODE95_WXY678'), (7,7,5,4,'2023-10-
15','CODE95_WXY679');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver_licence_category` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `driver_licence_category_type`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `driver_licence_category_type`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `driver_licence_category_type` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type` varchar(5) NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  UNIQUE KEY `type` (`type`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=16 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `driver_licence_category_type`
--

LOCK TABLES `driver_licence_category_type` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver_licence_category_type` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `driver_licence_category_type` VALUES
(2,'A'), (3,'A1'), (4,'A2'), (1,'AM'), (5,'B'), (7,'B1'), (6,'BE'), (10,'C'), (8,'C1'), (9,'
C1E'), (11,'CE'), (14,'D'), (12,'D1'), (13,'D1E'), (15,'DE');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver_licence_category_type` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `driver_licence_status`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `driver_licence_status`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `driver_licence_status` (

```

```

`id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
`status` varchar(20) NOT NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=7 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `driver_licence_status`
--

LOCK TABLES `driver_licence_status` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver_licence_status` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `driver_licence_status` VALUES
(1, 'VALID'), (2, 'EXPIRED'), (3, 'SUSPENDED'), (4, 'REVOKED'), (5, 'CONFISCATED'), (6, 'LOST/
STOLEN');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driver_licence_status` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `driving_interval`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `driving_interval`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `driving_interval` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `tachograph_card_id` int NOT NULL,
  `begin` timestamp NOT NULL,
  `end` timestamp NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `tachograph_card_id_idx` (`tachograph_card_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_driving_interval_tachograph_card` FOREIGN KEY
(`tachograph_card_id`) REFERENCES `tachograph_card` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=5 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `driving_interval`
--

LOCK TABLES `driving_interval` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driving_interval` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `driving_interval` VALUES (1,1,'2025-02-01 08:00:00','2025-02-01
12:00:00'), (2,1,'2025-02-02 09:00:00','2025-02-02 13:00:00'), (3,2,'2025-03-01
07:30:00','2025-03-01 11:30:00'), (4,3,'2025-04-01 10:00:00','2025-04-01 14:00:00');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `driving_interval` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `exceeding_time_limits`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `exceeding_time_limits`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;

```

```

CREATE TABLE `exceeding_time_limits` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type_id` int NOT NULL,
  `driver_id` int NOT NULL,
  `exceeded_hours` int NOT NULL,
  `exceeded_minutes` int NOT NULL,
  `exceeded_seconds` int NOT NULL,
  `tachograph_id` int NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `driver_id_idx` (`driver_id`),
  KEY `type_id_idx` (`type_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_exceeding_time_limits_con_driver` FOREIGN KEY (`driver_id`)
REFERENCES `driver` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_exceeding_time_limits_type` FOREIGN KEY (`type_id`) REFERENCES
`exceeding_time_limits_type` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=5 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

```

```

--
-- Dumping data for table `exceeding_time_limits`
--

```

```

LOCK TABLES `exceeding_time_limits` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `exceeding_time_limits` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `exceeding_time_limits` VALUES
(1,1,1,2,30,45,0),(2,2,1,1,15,0,0),(3,1,2,3,0,0,0),(4,3,3,0,45,30,0);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `exceeding_time_limits` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

```

```

--
-- Table structure for table `exceeding_time_limits_type`
--

```

```

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `exceeding_time_limits_type`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `exceeding_time_limits_type` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type` varchar(20) NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  UNIQUE KEY `type` (`type`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=4 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

```

```

--
-- Dumping data for table `exceeding_time_limits_type`
--

```

```

LOCK TABLES `exceeding_time_limits_type` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `exceeding_time_limits_type` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `exceeding_time_limits_type` VALUES
(1,'Daily'),(3,'Monthly'),(2,'Weekly');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `exceeding_time_limits_type` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

```

```

--

```

```
-- Table structure for table `exceeding_time_r_driving_interval`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `exceeding_time_r_driving_interval`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `exceeding_time_r_driving_interval` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `driving_interval_id` int NOT NULL,
  `exceeding_time_limit_id` int NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `driving_interval_id_idx` (`driving_interval_id`),
  KEY `exceeding_time_limit_id_idx` (`exceeding_time_limit_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_exceeding_time_interval_r_driving` FOREIGN KEY
(`driving_interval_id`) REFERENCES `driving_interval` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_exceeding_time_r_exceeding_limit` FOREIGN KEY
(`exceeding_time_limit_id`) REFERENCES `exceeding_time_limits` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=6 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `exceeding_time_r_driving_interval`
--

LOCK TABLES `exceeding_time_r_driving_interval` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `exceeding_time_r_driving_interval` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `exceeding_time_r_driving_interval` VALUES
(1,1,1), (2,1,2), (3,2,1), (4,3,3), (5,4,4);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `exceeding_time_r_driving_interval` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `inspection`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `inspection`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `inspection` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `vehicle_id` int NOT NULL,
  `revision_centre` varchar(50) NOT NULL,
  `expiration_date` date NOT NULL,
  `execution_date` date NOT NULL,
  `description` tinytext,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `revision_vehicle_idx` (`vehicle_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `inspection_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`vehicle_id`) REFERENCES `vehicle`
(`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=4 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `inspection`
--
```

```

LOCK TABLES `inspection` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `inspection` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `inspection` VALUES (1,1,'Revision Centre A','2025-12-31','2025-01-15','First inspection for truck ABC123'),(2,2,'Revision Centre B','2025-11-30','2025-02-20','Inspection for van DEF456'),(3,3,'Revision Centre C','2025-10-31','2025-03-25','Inspection for car GHI789');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `inspection` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `insurance`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `insurance`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `insurance` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `company_name` varchar(50) NOT NULL,
  `contract_number` varchar(50) NOT NULL,
  `begin_validity` date NOT NULL,
  `end_validity` date NOT NULL,
  `vehicle_id` int NOT NULL,
  `description` tinytext,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  UNIQUE KEY `contract_number` (`contract_number`),
  UNIQUE KEY `vehicle_id` (`vehicle_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_insurance_vehicle` FOREIGN KEY (`vehicle_id`) REFERENCES `vehicle` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=4 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `insurance`
--

LOCK TABLES `insurance` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `insurance` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `insurance` VALUES (1,'Insurance Co A','INS001','2025-01-01','2026-01-01',1,'Insurance for truck ABC123'),(2,'Insurance Co B','INS002','2025-02-01','2026-02-01',2,'Insurance for van DEF456'),(3,'Insurance Co C','INS003','2025-03-01','2026-03-01',3,'Insurance for car GHI789');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `insurance` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `owner`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `owner`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `owner` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `company_name` varchar(50) NOT NULL,
  `fiscal_identifier` varchar(16) NOT NULL,
  `description` tinytext,

```

```

    PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
    UNIQUE KEY `fiscal_identifier` (`fiscal_identifier`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `owner`
--

LOCK TABLES `owner` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `owner` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `owner` VALUES (1,'Owner Company A','OWN001','Leading owner company A'),(2,'Owner Company B','OWN002','Prestigious owner company B');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `owner` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `tachograph_card`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `tachograph_card`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `tachograph_card` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `tachograph_card_code` varchar(255) NOT NULL,
  `driver_id` int NOT NULL,
  `description` tinytext,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  UNIQUE KEY `driver_id` (`driver_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_tachograph_card_driver` FOREIGN KEY (`driver_id`) REFERENCES `driver` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=4 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `tachograph_card`
--

LOCK TABLES `tachograph_card` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `tachograph_card` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `tachograph_card` VALUES (1,'TACHO001',1,'Tachograph card for driver Mario Rossi'),(2,'TACHO002',2,'Tachograph card for driver Luigi Verdi'),(3,'TACHO003',3,'Tachograph card for driver Anna Bianchi');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `tachograph_card` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `traffic_violation`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `traffic_violation`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `traffic_violation` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,

```

```

`code` varchar(50) NOT NULL,
`country_code` varchar(2) NOT NULL,
`driver_id` int NOT NULL,
`fine` decimal(10,2) DEFAULT NULL,
`expiration_date` date DEFAULT NULL,
`payed` tinyint NOT NULL,
`payment_date` date DEFAULT NULL,
`validity_points` int NOT NULL,
`description` tinytext,
PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
KEY `driver_id_idx` (`driver_id`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_traffic_violation_driver` FOREIGN KEY (`driver_id`) REFERENCES
`driver` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=9 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `traffic_violation`
--

LOCK TABLES `traffic_violation` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `traffic_violation` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `traffic_violation` VALUES (1,'TV12345','IT',1,150.00,'2023-10-
15',1,'2023-09-01',-3,'Eccesso di velocità'),(2,'TV11111','IT',1,250.00,'2023-11-
01',0,NULL,-4,'Guida distratta'),(3,'TV67890','FR',2,200.00,'2023-11-01',0,NULL,-
5,'Guida in stato di ebbrezza'),(4,'TV22222','FR',2,300.00,'2023-12-01',1,'2023-10-
15',-2,'Sosta vietata'),(5,'TV11223','DE',3,100.00,'2023-12-01',1,'2023-10-10',-
2,'Sosta vietata'),(6,'TV33333','DE',3,500.00,'2024-01-01',0,NULL,-6,'Incidente con
fuga'),(7,'TV33445','ES',4,300.00,'2024-01-15',0,NULL,-6,'Incidente con
fuga'),(8,'TV55667','UK',5,50.00,'2024-02-01',1,'2023-11-15',-1,'Uso del telefono
alla guida');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `traffic_violation` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `traffic_violation_consequence`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `traffic_violation_consequence`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `traffic_violation_consequence` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `traffic_violation_id` int NOT NULL,
  `status_id` int NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `fk_traffic_violation_consequence_traffic_violation_status` (`status_id`),
  KEY `traffic_violation_id_idx` (`traffic_violation_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_traffic_violation_consequence_traffic_violation` FOREIGN KEY
(`traffic_violation_id`) REFERENCES `traffic_violation` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_traffic_violation_consequence_traffic_violation_status` FOREIGN
KEY (`status_id`) REFERENCES `traffic_violation_consequence_status` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=11 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--

```

```
-- Dumping data for table `traffic_violation_consequence`
--

LOCK TABLES `traffic_violation_consequence` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `traffic_violation_consequence` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `traffic_violation_consequence` VALUES
(1,1,4), (2,1,5), (3,6,1), (4,6,3), (5,2,1), (6,2,4), (7,7,5), (8,7,2), (9,3,5), (10,3,4);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `traffic_violation_consequence` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `traffic_violation_consequence_status`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `traffic_violation_consequence_status`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `traffic_violation_consequence_status` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type` varchar(20) NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  UNIQUE KEY `type` (`type`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=6 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `traffic_violation_consequence_status`
--

LOCK TABLES `traffic_violation_consequence_status` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `traffic_violation_consequence_status` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `traffic_violation_consequence_status` VALUES
(3,'CONFISCATION'), (4,'FINE'), (2,'REVOCATION'), (1,'SUSPENSION'), (5,'VALIDITY_POINT'
);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `traffic_violation_consequence_status` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `vehicle`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `vehicle`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `vehicle` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `plate_number` varchar(20) NOT NULL,
  `country_code` varchar(5) NOT NULL,
  `type` varchar(50) DEFAULT NULL,
  `make` varchar(50) NOT NULL,
  `model` varchar(50) NOT NULL,
  `description` tinytext,
  `owner_id` int NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  UNIQUE KEY `plate_number` (`plate_number`),
  KEY `vehicle_owner_idx` (`owner_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_vehicle_owner` FOREIGN KEY (`owner_id`) REFERENCES `owner` (`id`)
)
```

```

) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=4 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `vehicle`
--

LOCK TABLES `vehicle` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `vehicle` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `vehicle` VALUES (1,'ABC123','IT','Truck','Volvo','FH16','Heavy duty
truck',1), (2,'DEF456','IT','Van','Ford','Transit','Commercial
van',1), (3,'GHI789','IT','Car','Fiat','500','Compact car',2);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `vehicle` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;
/*!40103 SET TIME_ZONE=@OLD_TIME_ZONE */;

/*!40101 SET SQL_MODE=@OLD_SQL_MODE */;
/*!40014 SET FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS */;
/*!40014 SET UNIQUE_CHECKS=@OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS */;
/*!40101 SET CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT=@OLD_CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT */;
/*!40101 SET CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS=@OLD_CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS */;
/*!40101 SET COLLATION_CONNECTION=@OLD_COLLATION_CONNECTION */;
/*!40111 SET SQL_NOTES=@OLD_SQL_NOTES */;

```

12.1.5 Web app Back end Database

```

CREATE DATABASE IF NOT EXISTS `webapp_be` /*!40100 DEFAULT CHARACTER SET utf8mb4
COLLATE utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci */ /*!80016 DEFAULT ENCRYPTION='N' */;
USE `webapp_be`;
-- MySQL dump 10.13  Distrib 8.0.40, for Win64 (x86_64)
--
-- Host: 127.0.0.1    Database: webapp_be
--
-- Server version 8.0.32

/*!40101 SET @OLD_CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT=@@CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS=@@CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_COLLATION_CONNECTION=@@COLLATION_CONNECTION */;
/*!50503 SET NAMES utf8 */;
/*!40103 SET @OLD_TIME_ZONE=@@TIME_ZONE */;
/*!40103 SET TIME_ZONE='+00:00' */;
/*!40014 SET @OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS=@@UNIQUE_CHECKS, UNIQUE_CHECKS=0 */;
/*!40014 SET @OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@@FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS, FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=0 */;
/*!40101 SET @OLD_SQL_MODE=@@SQL_MODE, SQL_MODE='NO_AUTO_VALUE_ON_ZERO' */;
/*!40111 SET @OLD_SQL_NOTES=@@SQL_NOTES, SQL_NOTES=0 */;

--
-- Table structure for table `alert`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `alert`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `alert` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,

```

```

`type_id` int DEFAULT NULL,
`location_id` int DEFAULT NULL,
`userid` varchar(100) DEFAULT NULL,
`timestamp` datetime DEFAULT NULL,
`tripid` varchar(100) DEFAULT NULL,
`message` text,
PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
KEY `fk_alerttype` (`type_id`),
KEY `fk_alert_location` (`location_id`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_alert_location` FOREIGN KEY (`location_id`) REFERENCES `location`
(`id`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_alerttype` FOREIGN KEY (`type_id`) REFERENCES `alert_type` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=2 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `alert`
--

LOCK TABLES `alert` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `alert` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `alert` VALUES (1,1,1,'user123','2025-06-26 09:07:52','trip567','Long
queue at entrance gate');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `alert` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `alert_type`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `alert_type`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `alert_type` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `description` varchar(30) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=6 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `alert_type`
--

LOCK TABLES `alert_type` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `alert_type` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `alert_type` VALUES
(1,'GENERIC'),(2,'QUEUE AT GATE'),(3,'QUEUE AT PORT'),(4,'DELAY'),(5,'STRIKE');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `alert_type` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `check_detail`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `check_detail`;

```

```

/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `check_detail` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `check_type_id` int DEFAULT NULL,
  `invalidity_reason` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `comments` text,
  `payload_id` int DEFAULT NULL,
  `invalidity_confirmed` tinyint(1) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `fk_checktype` (`check_type_id`),
  KEY `fk_payload` (`payload_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_checktype` FOREIGN KEY (`check_type_id`) REFERENCES `check_type`
(`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_payload` FOREIGN KEY (`payload_id`) REFERENCES `payload` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=2 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `check_detail`
--

LOCK TABLES `check_detail` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `check_detail` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `check_detail` VALUES (1,1,'Expired license','License expired by 3
months',1,1);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `check_detail` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `check_type`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `check_type`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `check_type` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `description` varchar(30) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=6 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `check_type`
--

LOCK TABLES `check_type` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `check_type` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `check_type` VALUES
(1,'DRIVING_LICENSE'),(2,'TRAFFIC_VIOLATION'),(3,'TRANSPORT_DOCUMENT'),(4,'PDQC'),(
5,'TACHOGRAPH');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `check_type` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--

```

```
-- Table structure for table `coordinates`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `coordinates`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `coordinates` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `latitude` varchar(50) NOT NULL,
  `longitude` varchar(50) NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=3 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `coordinates`
--

LOCK TABLES `coordinates` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `coordinates` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `coordinates` VALUES (1,'45.4642','9.1900'),(2,'41.9028','12.4964');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `coordinates` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `inspection_location`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `inspection_location`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `inspection_location` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `description` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `coordinates_id` int DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `fk_inspection_coordinates` (`coordinates_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_inspection_coordinates` FOREIGN KEY (`coordinates_id`) REFERENCES
`coordinates` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=2 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `inspection_location`
--

LOCK TABLES `inspection_location` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `inspection_location` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `inspection_location` VALUES (1,'Checkpoint Milano',1);
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `inspection_location` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `inspection_log`
--
```

```

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `inspection_log`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client  = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `inspection_log` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `submission_time` datetime DEFAULT NULL,
  `userid` varchar(100) DEFAULT NULL,
  `tripid` varchar(100) DEFAULT NULL,
  `check_detail_id` int DEFAULT NULL,
  `location_id` int DEFAULT NULL,
  `final_note` text,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `fk_checkdetail` (`check_detail_id`),
  KEY `fk_inspectionlocation` (`location_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_checkdetail` FOREIGN KEY (`check_detail_id`) REFERENCES
`check_detail` (`id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_inspectionlocation` FOREIGN KEY (`location_id`) REFERENCES
`inspection_location` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=2 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client  = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `inspection_log`
--

LOCK TABLES `inspection_log` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `inspection_log` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `inspection_log` VALUES (1,'2025-06-26
09:07:52','user123','trip567',1,1,'Driver needs to renew license');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `inspection_log` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `location`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `location`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client  = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `location` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `description` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `coordinates_id` int DEFAULT NULL,
  `type` varchar(100) DEFAULT NULL,
  `international_code` varchar(20) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),
  KEY `fk_location_coordinates` (`coordinates_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_location_coordinates` FOREIGN KEY (`coordinates_id`) REFERENCES
`coordinates` (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=2 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client  = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `location`
--

```

```
LOCK TABLES `location` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `location` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `location` VALUES (1,'Port of Genoa',1,'PORT','ITGOA');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `location` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;

--
-- Table structure for table `payload`
--

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `payload`;
/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client      = @@character_set_client */;
/*!50503 SET character_set_client = utf8mb4 */;
CREATE TABLE `payload` (
  `id` int NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `content` text,
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=2 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8mb4
COLLATE=utf8mb4_0900_ai_ci;
/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `payload`
--

LOCK TABLES `payload` WRITE;
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `payload` DISABLE KEYS */;
INSERT INTO `payload` VALUES (1,'JSON Document with check result');
/*!40000 ALTER TABLE `payload` ENABLE KEYS */;
UNLOCK TABLES;
/*!40103 SET TIME_ZONE=@OLD_TIME_ZONE */;

/*!40101 SET SQL_MODE=@OLD_SQL_MODE */;
/*!40014 SET FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS */;
/*!40014 SET UNIQUE_CHECKS=@OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS */;
/*!40101 SET CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT=@OLD_CHARACTER_SET_CLIENT */;
/*!40101 SET CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS=@OLD_CHARACTER_SET_RESULTS */;
/*!40101 SET COLLATION_CONNECTION=@OLD_COLLATION_CONNECTION */;
/*!40111 SET SQL_NOTES=@OLD_SQL_NOTES */;
```

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